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**EXPLORING THE EFFECT OF AUDIOBOOK SEQUENCE ON EFL UNIVERSITY
STUDENTS' LEARNING**

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Biographical Sketch

Mason Williams graduated from Roanoke College in Virginia, USA, in 2008 with a Bachelor of Arts. Shortly after, in September 2008, he embarked on a career in English education by accepting a teaching position at an elementary school in South Korea, where he has lived ever since with his wife.

Over the years, Mason has gained extensive experience teaching English to a broad range of learners, including elementary, middle, and high school students, as well as university students and working professionals. With seven years of experience teaching at the university level, Mason has been employed as an assistant professor at Korea Nazarene University since 2021.

In addition to his teaching career, Mason pursued further academic growth by completing a Graduate Diploma in the LLE program through UPOU and is currently working toward his Master of Arts in Language and Literacy Education (MALLE) from the same institution.

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Dedication

I dedicate this work to my lovely wife, Hyewon, whose patience and unwavering support through God have guided me throughout my DLLE and MALLE journey at UPOU. Her encouragement during my struggles, as I balanced work, studies, and family, has been my greatest source of strength, and I am deeply grateful for her role in helping me achieve this milestone.

ABSTRACT

This exploratory small case study investigates the effects of two audiobook sequencing methods—Reading Before Listening (RBL) and Listening Before Reading (LBR)—on Korean university EFL students' reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and motivation to read. The study aimed to determine whether one sequencing approach offered stronger outcomes and whether alternating the two could enhance learning. Three students participated in switching sequencing methods midway through the study. Data were collected through formative assessments, pre- and post-surveys, reading logs, group discussions, and guided interviews.

Findings indicate that RBL sequencing supported stronger spelling accuracy and comprehension, while LBR sequencing helped students grasp broader meaning and develop listening strategies. Students who began with RBL and switched to LBR showed noticeable gains in comprehension, while those who switched from LBR to RBL demonstrated improved spelling accuracy. Despite the small sample size and an early participant dropout, consistent engagement and learner strategy development were observed across cases.

These results support theories of Cognitive Load, Dual Coding, and Transfer Stage theory, highlighting the cognitive benefits of multimodal input and strategic sequencing. The study offers practical implications for educators aiming to integrate audiobooks into reading programs, suggesting that flexible sequencing—tailored to learner needs—can enhance both comprehension and spelling outcomes. Future research should involve larger samples, varied text types, and classroom-based implementations to build on these initial insights.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	v
Acknowledgements	vi
Dedication	vii
TABLE OF CONTENTS	ix
LIST OF TABLES	xii
LIST OF FIGURES	xii
ABSTRACT	viii
CHAPTER 1	1
INTRODUCTION	1
Background of the Study	3
Rationale for Studying Audiobook Sequencing	4
Potential Benefits of Studying Audiobook Sequence	6
The Context of Korea and Challenges in Korean Education	8
Research Objectives	9
Research Questions	10
Assumption	10
Significance of the Study	11
Scope of the Study	12
CHAPTER 2	13
LITERATURE REVIEW	13
Introduction	13
Theoretical Framework	15
Reading and Development of Comprehension in the Digital Age	18
Audiobooks and Reading: Usage and Impact	21
Spelling Accuracy and the Role of Listening in EFL Learning	25
Motivation in Reading in Second Language Acquisition to Audiobook Sequencing	27
Challenges in the Korean EFL Classroom	31
Conclusion	32
Conceptual Framework	33
Operational Use of Terms	35
CHAPTER 3	37
METHODOLOGY	37
Research Design	37
Participants	39
Participant Profiles	40

Selection Criteria	41
Locale and Context	43
Data Collection and Tools	45
Instruments	46
Instrument Validation and Revisions	58
RBL and LBR Administration	60
Timeline	62
Data Analysis	65
Quantitative Analysis	66
Qualitative Analysis	67
Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Findings	72
Justification for Manual Analysis	72
Limitations	73
CHAPTER 4:	75
PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA	75
Introduction	75
Summary of Participants	76
The Case of Student 1 (S1)	78
The Case of Student 2 (S2)	80
The Case of Student 3 (S3)	84
Summary of Student Cases	87
CHAPTER 5	93
SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, & RECOMMENDATIONS	93
Summary of Key Findings	93
Sequencing Effects and Theoretical Alignment:	96
Conclusion	97
Confirmation of Assumptions	98
Recommendations	100
Limitations	100
REFERENCES	102
APPENDICES	123
APPENDIX A: ORIGINAL AND REVISED PRE-SURVEY	123
Original Pre-Survey	123
Revised Pre Survey	128
APPENDIX B: ORIGINAL AND REVISED POST SURVEY	135
Original Post Survey	135
Revised Post Survey	138
APPENDIX C: CONSENT FORM	141
APPENDIX D: ORIGINAL AND REVISED CHAPTERS 1-12 AND 13-27 QUIZZES	145
Original Quiz	

145Revised Quiz	154
APPENDIX E: ORIGINAL AND REVISED READING/LISTENING LOG	162
Original Log	162
Revised Log	164
APPENDIX F: PRE-SURVEY RESULTS	168
APPENDIX G: SUMMARY OF POST SURVEY LIKERT-STYLE RESPONSES (Questions 4a–12a)	175
APPENDIX H: STUDENT READING LOGS (Students 1-3)	177
APPENDIX I: STUDENTS' ANSWERS TO THE TESTS	198

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1	18
Theoretical Frameworks Underpinning Audiobook Use in Language Learning	18
Table 2:	23
Comparative Overview of Audiobook Studies	23
Table 3	29
Key Studies on Learning Motivation	29
Table 4:	48
Quiz Composition Before and After Validation	48
Table 5:	58
Summary of Validator Feedback and Action Taken	58
Table 6:	63
Research Schedule	63

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1	34
Conceptual Framework	34
Figure 2:	38
Research Process Flowchart	38
Figure 3	87
Bar graph on quiz scores before and after each sequence	87
Figure 4	95
Sequencing Effects on EFL Learners' Reading Comprehension, Spelling Accuracy, and Motivation	95

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Audiobooks have emerged as a dynamic tool in reading, offering both avid and reluctant readers accessible literary options. As Matthew Rubery aptly noted, "Audiobooks are for people who hate reading and for those of us who love reading" (Clemens, 2021). The global audiobook industry is projected to reach \$35 billion by 2030 (Curcic, 2023), reflecting a significant shift in literary engagement. This trend is particularly pronounced in South Korea, where audiobook consumption has surged in recent years (Korean Times, 2023).

Bright (2024) concludes in her thesis that audiobooks are widely valued by librarians, teachers, and parents for their educational benefits. However, understanding the effects of audiobooks on reading comprehension, spelling, and motivation remains critical in language acquisition, especially in EFL contexts. According to Buecksler (2024), audiobooks support literacy development through seven key benefits: 1) Auditory learning and a multisensory approach that engages different learning styles; 2) Access to vocabulary, helping learners acquire new words in context; 3) Increased comprehension by providing auditory scaffolding; 4) Access to grade-level material that might otherwise be inaccessible; 5) Flexibility and accessibility, enabling learning anytime and anywhere; 6) Encouragement of learner independence; and 7) Promotion of enjoyment and motivation to engage with texts. These benefits suggest that audiobooks can aid not only comprehension but also spelling, by reinforcing the

connection between sounds and written forms. Nevertheless, challenges persist, such as potential over-reliance on listening and the need to integrate audiobooks thoughtfully with traditional reading practices to promote balanced language development.

Building on the benefits of multisensory learning through audiobooks, research supports the effectiveness of combining auditory and visual inputs in language acquisition. A study by Rogowsky, Calhoun, and Tallal (2016) highlights the effectiveness of dual-modality learning—combining auditory and visual inputs—in foreign language classrooms, demonstrating gains in comprehension without significant differences in test scores when compared to standalone reading.

Such findings are particularly relevant in South Korea, where a decline in reading engagement among university students is concerning. According to a report by the Ministry of Education, over a quarter of students no longer read for leisure outside of academic requirements (Jang, 2017; Yoo 2020). This trend underscores the need for innovative approaches, as the education system has traditionally emphasized memorization, limiting opportunities for deeper comprehension and critical thinking (Lee, 2019; DeWaelsche, 2015). Rahn (2018) advocates for educational reforms that prioritize curiosity and intrinsic motivation over academic achievement alone.

Building on this perspective, this study investigates whether audiobook sequencing—Listening Before Reading (LBR) and Reading Before Listening (RBL)—can foster a more engaging learning experience. By exploring the potential benefits of different sequencing strategies, this research aims to fill a gap in understanding how the

audiobook order affects language learning outcomes by offering insights for educators seeking to enhance English language instruction in Korea.

Background of the Study

In recent years, the integration of technology into language learning has garnered significant attention, particularly the use of audiobooks as supplementary tools for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners (Kim, 2021; Lhamo & Salkuwongs, 2023). Audiobooks provide learners with access to authentic language input, supporting the development of listening skills, pronunciation, and comprehension (Chang, 2011; Kim 2019; Kim, 2021). Unlike traditional text-based learning, audiobooks combine auditory and textual modalities, which can cater to diverse learning preferences and foster greater engagement (Bright, 2024). The growing popularity of audiobooks in educational contexts underscores the need to explore their pedagogical potential further.

However, while the general benefits of audiobooks are well-documented (Gorelik, 2017; Best, 2020), there appears to be a lack of research specifically examining how sequencing—whether listening precedes or follows reading—affects learning outcomes. This study aims to address this gap by investigating the effects of two audiobook sequences: Reading Before Listening (RBL) and Listening Before Reading (LBR), on Korean university students' reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and intrinsic motivation to read. Spelling accuracy was included due to its importance in literacy development and because spelling is often affected by the type and order of language input (Ehri, 2000; Treiman & Kessler, 2005). Although audiobooks may

promote recognition and pronunciation, it is unclear whether they enhance or hinder orthographic retention, especially when compared to reading-first approaches. By focusing on sequencing, this research seeks to provide insights into how audiobooks can be effectively incorporated into EFL curricula.

Rationale for Studying Audiobook Sequencing

The use of **audiobooks** as a pedagogical tool in **EFL education** has gained increasing recognition due to their potential to enhance language acquisition. Research suggests that audiobooks support vocabulary development (Montgomery, 2009), pronunciation improvement (Saka, 2015), and overall language competence (Alcantud-Diaz & Gregori-Signes, 2014). Additionally, studies indicate that students generally perceive audiobooks positively (Tusmagambet, 2020). In particular, Laroui and Chelli (2015) found that audiobooks significantly improve EFL learners' listening comprehension, highlighting their value as a multimodal learning resource.

However, while prior research highlights the benefits of audiobooks, it does not examine whether the sequencing of audiobook use—reading before listening (RBL) versus listening before reading (LBR)—affects comprehension, spelling accuracy, or motivation. The present study addresses this gap by investigating how audiobook sequencing affects Korean university students' reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and intrinsic motivation to read.

From a theoretical standpoint, Fries' Reading Readiness Theory (1963) suggests that oral comprehension mastery forms the foundation of reading development. This

raises the question of whether a particular sequencing of listening and reading could optimize learning outcomes. Similarly, Dual Coding Theory (Paivio, 1986) proposes that presenting material in both auditory and visual formats leads to richer cognitive processing, potentially making audiobook sequencing a valuable instructional approach.

In the Korean EFL context, where rote memorization is widely practiced (Green, 2022), innovative methods like audiobook sequencing could offer an alternative that fosters deeper engagement. Many Korean university students perceive reading in English as challenging and disengaging, reinforcing the need for approaches that not only support language development but also sustain motivation.

In addition to comprehension and motivation, spelling accuracy was included as a core outcome in this study. Accurate spelling remains a foundational component of English literacy and is closely linked to reading proficiency (Ehri, 2000). This connection is especially relevant in contexts where learners rely heavily on memorization, as in many Korean EFL classrooms. Moreover, lexical sophistication, including accurate word form retrieval, has been shown to support comprehensible second language production (Saito, Webb, Trofimovich, & Isaacs, 2016), highlighting the broader role of orthographic knowledge in communication. Therefore, examining whether RBL or LBR sequencing better supports reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and orthographic retention could offer practical insights into optimizing audiobook-based literacy instruction for Korean university EFL students.

To ensure clarity and consistency throughout the thesis, it is important to explain the relationship between spelling accuracy and retention. In this study, spelling

accuracy was used as a measurable indicator of orthographic retention—that is, students’ ability to visually recognize and correctly reproduce English words after exposure through reading and/or listening. While “retention” can encompass broader cognitive outcomes, here it refers specifically to the internalization of spelling forms. This clarification supports a more accurate interpretation of the study's findings related to students’ spelling performance.

By exploring the effects of sequencing on crucial language learning outcomes, this research strives to inform the effective use of audiobooks in Korean university EFL classrooms.

Potential Benefits of Studying Audiobook Sequence

Research shows that audiobooks have a positive effect on language learning, with studies highlighting gains in vocabulary acquisition, pronunciation, and literacy skills (Alcantud-Diaz & Gregori-Signes, 2014; Montgomery, 2009; Saka, 2015). In addition, Tusmagambet (2020) reported favorable attitudes toward audiobooks among Kazakh EFL students. However, few studies have examined how sequencing—whether listening precedes or follows reading—affects specific learning outcomes. This study seeks to fill this gap by analyzing how sequencing affects reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and motivation to read, providing valuable insights into optimizing EFL instruction.

While existing literature explores audiobook benefits, there remains limited understanding of how the sequencing of audiobook use—listening before or after

reading—affects learning outcomes. This study addresses this by investigating how different audiobook sequences (LBR and RBL) influence key areas of language learning, including reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and intrinsic motivation to read. Understanding whether auditory exposure before or after reading improves comprehension and spelling accuracy can help refine language instruction strategies in EFL classrooms.

Studying audiobook sequencing is especially relevant in Korea, where traditional reading habits have declined (Korea Times, 2016), posing challenges for educators attempting to engage university students with English literature. Insights gained from this study could assist educators in better integrating audiobooks into their teaching, helping students improve reading comprehension and spelling accuracy while fostering a greater motivation to read.

Gorelik (2017) highlights seven key ways audiobooks can benefit struggling students:

1. Increase word exposure and improve vocabulary
2. Build background knowledge
3. Reduce working memory deficit
4. Alleviate printed word decoding anxiety
5. Improve comprehension
6. Develop grade-appropriate content knowledge
7. Provide educational freedom

These benefits highlight audiobooks' transformative potential in EFL classrooms, particularly for students who may struggle with traditional reading approaches (Koskinen et al., 2000; Wolfson, 2008). By examining audiobook sequencing, this study aims to further maximize these benefits, fostering a more engaging and effective learning environment.

The Context of Korea and Challenges in Korean Education

Reading engagement among South Korean university students has significantly declined, as Jang (2017) reports that many students no longer engage in reading for pleasure. This trend highlights the need for more engaging approaches, as the education system's emphasis on rote memorization has led to notable gaps in both comprehension and critical thinking skills (Lee, 2019; DeWaeltsche, 2015). Rahn (2018) suggests that reform efforts should prioritize curiosity-driven learning and intrinsic motivation rather than passive memorization.

With over seven years of experience teaching English at the university level, I have observed that students often prioritize memorization techniques to pass exams, frequently neglecting exploratory and analytical reading approaches. This aligns with findings from Kwak (2020) and DeWaeltsche (2015), who note a strong tendency among Korean students to rely on test-focused memorization strategies rather than actively engage with texts. Additionally, Jeon (2010) observes that Korean students' English listening skills continue to lag behind global averages, while Green (2022) highlights the

inherent limitations of memorization-based learning in developing well-rounded language proficiency.

By incorporating audiobooks, and examining the sequence of listening and reading activities, this study explores an alternative method that could bridge these gaps by enhancing language acquisition and fostering a deeper motivation to read in Korean EFL classrooms.

Research Objectives

1. To explore the effects of two audiobook sequencing methods (RBL and LBR) on the reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and intrinsic motivation of EFL university students in Korea.
2. To investigate EFL learners' experiences, engagement, and motivation to read when using different audiobook sequencing methods.
3. To analyze individual cases of Korean EFL students and their responses to the two audiobook sequencing methods (RBL and LBR), focusing on their comprehension, spelling accuracy, engagement, motivation, and reflections on learning behaviors.

Research Questions

1. What is the effect of RBL on selected university EFL students':
 - a. reading comprehension?

- b. spelling?
 - c. intrinsic motivation to read?
- 2. What is the effect of LBR on selected university EFL students':
 - a. reading comprehension?
 - b. spelling?
 - c. intrinsic motivation to read?

Assumption

An assumption is that if students listen to an audiobook before reading the text, their retention and comprehension of the material will improve. By engaging with the spoken form of the language first, students may find it easier to understand the text when they read it, as they will have already familiarized themselves with the vocabulary and sentence structure. As Richards and Rodgers (2001) explain, language skills are more effectively acquired when learners are first exposed to the spoken form before encountering the written text. This aural-oral training lays a crucial foundation for developing other language skills.

Conversely, if reading occurs before listening, students might demonstrate higher initial spelling accuracy due to their exposure to the written form first. However, it is anticipated that spelling accuracy will improve after the Listening Before Reading (LBR) method, as listening provides exposure to correct pronunciation patterns, which may later influence their spelling decisions.

Regarding motivation, this study does not make any specific assumptions. Instead, it seeks to explore how audiobook sequencing might influence students'

intrinsic motivation to read, recognizing motivation as a complex and multifaceted construct that requires careful investigation rather than presupposition.

Significance of the Study

This study has the potential to benefit the following stakeholders:

- **EFL Teachers:** It can provide insights into how resources like audiobooks might be integrated into classroom practices to enhance student engagement and comprehension. It will also offer recommendations on effective sequencing strategies (RBL vs. LBR) for optimizing student outcomes.
- **University Students:** It can offer a more engaging approach to language learning that may foster a greater enjoyment of reading and improve their English proficiency. Additionally, it may increase motivation by providing an alternative to traditional rote memorization.
- **Researchers and Academics:** It can contribute to the body of literature on the role of audiobook sequencing in EFL contexts, particularly in the collegiate setting in Korea. The study has also enriched the current understanding of multimedia learning strategies in EFL education.

Scope of the Study

This study focused on a small sample of Korean university students in a specific context, using the novel **Animorphs** as the primary text. The research specifically explored two audiobook sequencing methods—**Reading Before Listening (RBL)** and

Listening Before Reading (LBR)—and their effects on reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and intrinsic motivation to read.

While the findings are not broadly generalizable, they offer valuable insights that can inform similar educational settings and guide future research on the effects of audiobook sequencing in language acquisition. This research was conducted in a controlled setting with students previously enrolled in Practical English courses at a university in Korea.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

In recent years, the rapid shift towards digital tools in education has transformed reading and language learning, especially in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) contexts. This shift has expanded literacy modalities, with e-books and audiobooks offering multisensory engagement often absent in traditional print materials. However, while research has explored multimedia's potential to enhance comprehension and engagement (Ayunda, 2013; Friedland et al., 2017; Kim, 2021; Lhamo & Salkuwongs, 2023), the specific effects of audiobook sequencing remain underexplored, particularly for university students learning English in EFL contexts, especially in South Korea.

Researchers agree that multimodal resources like audiobooks can enhance comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, and learner motivation. For instance, Spjeldnæs and Karlsen (2022) found that combining audio and visual elements supports understanding by offering learners different ways to process content. Additionally, Kim (2021) highlights the potential of digital tools in supporting high-level literacy skills among university students. Audiobooks have also been found to improve learners' word recognition and spelling by reinforcing sound-symbol connections during reading tasks (Baskin & Harris, 1995; Biancarosa & Snow, 2006).

However, questions remain about how the sequence of listening and reading might affect learners differently based on their language proficiency, age, or engagement levels.

This study specifically addresses these questions by exploring the effects of two audiobook sequencing methods — Listening Before Reading (LBR) and Reading Before Listening (RBL) — on reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and motivation among South Korean university EFL learners. By examining how the order of multimodal input influences learning outcomes and learner attitudes, the research aims to fill gaps in understanding the optimal integration of audiobooks in EFL contexts.

Research into audiobook use in EFL settings has primarily focused on its benefits for developing listening comprehension and reading fluency. For example, Rahman and Hajar (2020) reported that high school students who used audiobooks showed measurable improvements in listening comprehension and reading fluency, demonstrating the effectiveness of combining auditory input with text to support language development. Rahman and Hajar also noted increased learner confidence in pronunciation and listening skills, which can contribute to greater engagement with English learning materials. Similarly, Bright (2024) emphasizes that audiobooks encourage enjoyment and independence in reading, while Buecksler (2024) highlights how audiobooks foster engagement by providing flexible, multisensory learning experiences that increase learner motivation and confidence.

Furthermore, studies indicate that the sequence of engagement with audiobooks may influence not only comprehension but also spelling accuracy and retention, as seen

in Chang's (2011) work with Taiwanese students, who exhibited stronger vocabulary retention when combining reading with listening activities. Further studies, such as Zarei and Rashvand (2011), also found that EFL learners exposed to audio-assisted reading displayed improved spelling accuracy, suggesting that repeated exposure to correct word forms may reinforce orthographic knowledge.

This review will examine existing literature across several themes: reading comprehension in the digital age, the role of audiobooks in reading development, the influence of multimodality on spelling and vocabulary acquisition, and motivation in reading. As summarized in Table 1, these themes provide a foundation for understanding how audiobook sequencing may enhance reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and intrinsic motivation among EFL learners in South Korea. Additionally, this review highlights the need for further research on sequencing approaches within audiobook usage, as existing studies largely focus on simultaneous reading-listening methods rather than sequential formats that may hold distinct pedagogical benefits.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in several interrelated theoretical frameworks that collectively inform our understanding of how audiobook sequencing can enhance reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and intrinsic motivation among EFL learners.

The primary theories guiding this study are Dual Coding Theory, Cognitive Load Theory, and Transfer Stage Theory. These frameworks provide critical insights into how multimodal input, cognitive processing, and sequencing order affect language learning outcomes.

Dual Coding Theory (Paivio, 1986) asserts that information presented through both verbal and visual modalities is more effectively processed. Audiobooks, which combine auditory input with accompanying visual texts, exemplify this duality, allowing learners to engage with content holistically and improving their reading comprehension and vocabulary acquisition. Additionally, by engaging both the phonological loop and visual input systems, dual coding may support orthographic mapping, a crucial process for spelling development (Ehri, 2013).

Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988) builds on this concept by proposing that learners' cognitive resources are limited, and that when information is distributed across multiple channels, the cognitive load on each channel can be minimized. In multimedia learning research, Mayer (2005) demonstrates that combining audio with visual text can help reduce cognitive load, enhancing comprehension and retention. For EFL learners, dual-modality processing through listening and reading may efficiently support language structure and vocabulary processing. Therefore, in the study's context, audiobook sequencing—RBL and LBR—is assumed to leverage these dual-coding benefits to support reading comprehension and spelling retention.

Transfer Stage Theory (Fries, 1945) is also relevant, as it suggests that oral language is learned first, followed by written language, with overlapping skills. Fries's

framework suggests that combining listening (oral) with reading (written) can create a more comprehensive learning experience. By analyzing the sequences of “reading before listening” (RBL) or “listening before reading” (LBR), this study aims to identify specific skills that students struggle with and determine which method proves most effective for learning among Korean university students.

While these three theories form the core foundation of this study, additional insights are drawn from Constructivist Learning Theory (Piaget, 1952; Vygotsky, 1978) and Krashen and Terrell’s (1983) Natural Approach. Constructivist Learning Theory highlights the value of interactive, multimodal resources in fostering knowledge construction, while the Natural Approach suggests that authentic materials like audiobooks can support natural language acquisition.

As summarized in **Table 1**, these theories collectively highlight the role of multimodal engagement in reducing cognitive load and improving accuracy. They also suggest that different sequencing patterns may influence not only how learners process language, but also how they encode it into long-term memory, particularly in relation to spelling and vocabulary development.

Table 1

Theoretical Frameworks Underpinning Audiobook Use in Language Learning

Theory	Key Concepts	Application to Audiobook Sequencing	Key References
--------	--------------	--	----------------

Dual Coding Theory	Verbal-visual processing for better retention	Audiobooks can enhance comprehension through integrated audio-visual modes	Paivio (1986)
Cognitive Load Theory	Minimize cognitive load across channels	Reduces cognitive load through dual-channel processing	Sweller (1988), Mayer (2005)
Transfer Stage (Fries)	Oral precedes written language	Investigates impact of LBR vs. RBL on language skill transfer	Fries (1945)

Reading and Development of Comprehension in the Digital Age

As digital technologies continue to redefine literacy, multimodal approaches such as audiobooks have gained increasing attention for their potential to enhance reading comprehension through combined auditory and visual engagement. Multimodal literacy—the ability to interpret and create meaning through multiple modes including audio, text, and visuals—is central to understanding how learners interact with digital texts (Kress, 2003; Cope & Kalantzis, 2009).

Studies have explored how various digital tools support literacy development, ranging from exploratory descriptions of technology use to explanatory and impact-focused research. For example, Plowman and Stephen (2003) discuss how digital

technologies create interactive and learner-centered environments that promote engagement and comprehension. These general investigations establish the broad potential of digital tools to influence literacy learning across different age groups and proficiency levels.

Among digital resources, e-books and audiobooks are frequently highlighted for their ability to provide rich, multisensory learning experiences. Spjeldnæs and Karlsen (2022) found that such formats enhance comprehension by engaging learners through both visual and auditory channels, supporting a more holistic literacy skill set. Friedland et al. (2017) suggest that younger or less fluent readers especially benefit from these tools. Meanwhile, Kim (2021) studied Korean university students and noted that while ebooks and audiobooks both support comprehension, using them simultaneously might hinder the development of independent reading skills.

Research specifically focused on audiobook use shows promising outcomes in areas such as word recognition, vocabulary acquisition, and spelling accuracy, due to their reinforcement of sound-symbol connections during reading tasks (Baskin & Harris, 1995; Biancarosa & Snow, 2006). However, most studies examine audiobook usage broadly—often emphasizing simultaneous audio-text input— without addressing the effects of sequencing—whether learners read before listening or listen before reading.

One earlier relevant study is Bagget (1981), who investigated sequencing with movies combining images and auditory input, though not paired with written text. This research demonstrated that the order of presenting visual and auditory information could influence comprehension and retention. Bagget's findings suggest that

sequencing is an important factor worth exploring in multimedia learning contexts, including audiobook use.

Mayer's research highlights how sequencing order in multimedia learning environments can affect comprehension and retention. Mayer's Segmenting Principle, a key concept within multimedia learning theory, suggests that breaking content into smaller, manageable segments can reduce cognitive load (Mayer, 2009; Sweller, 1988) and enhance learner comprehension and retention. In addition, Mayer's Modality Principle emphasizes that people learn better from graphics and narration than from graphics and on-screen text alone, suggesting that pairing auditory and visual channels can maximize working memory efficiency (Mayer, 2009). When applied to audiobooks, this principle indicates that sequencing—whether students read before listening or listen before reading—could influence how well they understand and remember the material.

Further, Mayer's Temporal Contiguity Principle asserts that learning is improved when corresponding verbal and visual information are presented simultaneously rather than successively. This raises important questions about whether aligning text and audio input—either concurrently or sequentially—affects comprehension differently, particularly for EFL learners. If text and narration are sequenced too far apart, learners may struggle to integrate the information effectively, especially when processing in a non-native language.

Despite the growing recognition of audiobook benefits, none of the studies reviewed—with the exception of Bagget (1981), who examined sequencing with movies combining images and audio but not paired with written text—specifically investigate the

distinct effects of sequencing reading before listening (RBL) versus listening before reading (LBR) among university-level EFL learners. This study addresses that gap by exploring how sequencing influences reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and motivation among Korean university students, aiming to provide practical insights for optimizing EFL instruction and learner engagement.

Audiobooks and Reading: Usage and Impact

Audiobooks have been studied extensively for their potential to enhance reading comprehension, fluency, and vocabulary acquisition in EFL settings (Kim, 2021; Aka, 2023; Lhamo & Salkuwongs, 2023). A key distinction in the literature is between “simultaneous-mode” studies, which pair text and audio at the same time (RWL/LWR), and sequencing studies—still unexplored—which arranges audio and text in separate phases (RBL or LBR).

Simultaneous-mode research—for example, Ayunda (2013) and Friedland et al. (2017)—has shown that listening while reading or reading while listening enhances fluency and comprehension; Kim (2021) demonstrated comprehension gains but noted potential limits on independent reading skills when both modalities are combined. Best (2020) found that dual-input supports struggling readers’ vocabulary and engagement. Rahman & Hajar (2020) reported that dramatized audiobooks increase pronunciation confidence and motivation.

However, no research has been found that directly examines the effects of sequencing these modalities in audiobook use—specifically, whether learners benefit more from listening before reading (LBR) or reading before listening (RBL)—with the

exception of Baggett (1981), whose study investigated the sequencing of narration and visuals in film viewing rather than audiobooks. Therefore, this study emphasizes sequential learning: listening to an audiobook prior to reading the text or reading first before listening to the audiobook.

Across diverse contexts, studies have documented audiobooks' broad benefits while also pointing to the need for tailored approaches based on student proficiency levels. In Indonesia, Ayunda (2013) revealed that repeated podcast listening improved fluency among 19–23-year-olds and recommended further research on low-proficiency learners. In rural Uganda, Friedland et al. (2017) showed elementary students who read while listening outperformed those who only read, despite limited technological resources. Aka (2023) in Japan found that high school students with lower proficiency gained vocabulary and fluency through reading while listening, though proficient peers saw smaller gains. In Korea, Kim (2021) observed that university students benefit from simultaneous ebook and audiobook use for comprehension but may not develop deep, independent reading skills—underscoring the need to explore sequencing methods. Finally, Lhamo & Salkuwongs (2023) in Bhutan concluded that audiobooks of poems significantly improved fifth graders' comprehension and motivation. Together, these findings highlight the critical gap in research on sequencing modalities shown in Table 2.

Table 2:*Comparative Overview of Audiobook Studies*

Context	Study	Focus	Key Findings
Indonesia	Ayunda (2013)	Impact of podcasts on fluency among Indonesian EFL students.	Repeated listening led to improvements in fluency.
Uganda	Friedland et al. (2017)	Effect of audiobooks on fluency in a rural Ugandan school.	Improved fluency observed in students who read while listening.
Japan	Aka (2023)	Benefits of audiobooks on vocabulary and fluency for Japanese EFL	Audiobooks benefited struggling readers' vocabulary and fluency.

		learners.	
Korea	Kim (2021)	Effects of ebooks and audiobooks on comprehension for Korean university students.	Simultaneous use of reading and listening supports comprehension but may limit independent reading.
Bhutan	Lhamo and Salkuwongs (2023)	Impact of audiobook poems on reading comprehension and motivation in Bhutanese students.	Positive influence on reading comprehension and motivation.

Understanding how audiobooks are utilized in EFL contexts is crucial for seeing how learners build knowledge inside and outside the classroom. Abadiano and Turner (2005, p. 25) emphasize “modeling is essential to fluency development” (Keehn, Harmon, & Shoho, 2008, p. 339) in Reader’s Theater, an insight that applies equally to audiobook modeling. Wolfson (2008) likewise argues that audiobooks can teach reading

by providing a clear model for listeners, though he cautions they should supplement rather than replace silent reading.

These findings underscore the widespread potential of audiobooks to support EFL learners, while also highlighting the critical gap in research on sequencing the modalities which is a gap this study aims to fill.

Spelling Accuracy and the Role of Listening in EFL Learning

Research on the relationship between listening practices and spelling accuracy remains limited yet crucial for this study. Al-Jarf (2005) demonstrated that EFL freshmen with stronger listening comprehension and decoding skills achieved significantly higher spelling scores, indicating that auditory processing underpins orthographic development. Kim (2019) further observed that university students often outperform in reading comprehension relative to listening, suggesting that targeted listening activities could balance these skill sets and potentially boost spelling accuracy.

Evidence from dual-modality studies underscores the promise of combining audio and text. Chang (2011) found that Taiwanese high-schoolers who read while listening to audiobooks gained more vocabulary and listening proficiency than peers who read alone. Kim (2021) reported that pairing ebooks with audiobooks enhanced comprehension, while Albeshir (2018) highlighted that integrated audio exposure helps Saudi EFL learners overcome phonological spelling errors. Dich and Pedersen (2013) showed that learners' L1 orthographic systems influence EFL spelling accuracy, pointing to the need for modality-specific interventions, and Saito et al. (2023)

emphasized that robust phonological vocabulary knowledge is key to both listening proficiency and spelling accuracy.

Cognitive and applied-media research offers further insight. Baggett (1981) found that reading before listening yields better retention than simultaneous presentation, whereas Varao Sousa, Carriere, and Smilek (2013) showed that single-modality tasks can increase mind-wandering, undermining retention. Age and proficiency also shape outcomes as Pillai and Yathiraj (2017) reported greater benefits of auditory learning for younger learners, while Baron (2021) and Brown (2011) observed that adult learners exhibit superior recall and spelling mastery after reading. Fresch (2008) argued that strong reading–writing habits enhance mental visualization of words, further bolstering orthographic memory.

However, no study to date has isolated the effects of sequencing audiobook listening and reading on spelling accuracy in university-level EFL contexts—a gap this research seeks to fill. With the exception of Baggett (1981), who examined sequencing in film narration rather than audiobooks, this area remains largely unexplored.

Motivation in Reading in Second Language Acquisition to Audiobook

Sequencing

Motivation plays a pivotal role in reading development, directly influencing student engagement and text retention. Studies by Divoll and Browning (2013) underscore that without intrinsic motivation—rooted in personal interest and enjoyment—reading retention can be challenging, especially among university students.

Their "Reading Retention Strategy" (RRS) aimed to foster motivation in the absence of grade-based pressure, highlighting the importance of strategies that promote voluntary reading engagement.

In the context of second language acquisition (SLA), motivation is considered one of the most critical affective factors (Dörnyei, 1998). Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985) distinguishes between intrinsic motivation, where students engage in reading for enjoyment or personal growth, and extrinsic motivation, where reading is driven by external pressures such as grades or course requirements. Chon (2017) highlighted that university students often read more for extrinsic reasons, such as fulfilling academic requirements, rather than for intrinsic enjoyment. This aligns with Dörnyei's (2005) L2 Motivational Self System, which suggests that students' motivation is influenced by their L2 personal aspirations and their L2 external obligations.

Table 3 below summarizes key studies on motivation in second language acquisition and audiobook sequencing, highlighting theoretical foundations and empirical findings relevant to this study.

Studies on audiobook integration suggest that audiobooks may enhance intrinsic motivation by making reading more accessible and engaging. Kartal and Simsek (2017) found that Turkish EFL learners who used audiobooks were more likely to continue reading outside the classroom, demonstrating increased intrinsic motivation. Saito et al. (2023) also noted that individual differences in learners' engagement with oral input could be linked to variations in motivation, suggesting that auditory learning tools may influence learner identity and self-regulation. In addition, Albeshir (2018) noted that

students who used multi-sensory approaches, such as audio-assisted reading, expressed greater willingness to continue reading in English.

With the increasing availability of digital reading platforms, technology has also shaped students' access to audiobooks, influencing how and when they engage with texts. This suggests that the sequencing of audiobooks and traditional reading may not only enhance comprehension but also influence motivation, encouraging students to shift from extrinsically motivated reading habits to intrinsic engagement.

Additionally, Expectancy-Value Theory (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002) suggests that students are more likely to engage in reading if they perceive it as valuable and believe they can succeed. The use of audiobooks, particularly when sequenced strategically, may increase both perceived value (by making texts more engaging) and expectancy of success (by reducing cognitive load and improving comprehension). This study will examine whether the sequencing of audiobooks and reading affects students' motivation to engage with texts, potentially fostering a more self-directed and meaningful reading experience.

Given these considerations, diverse approaches to reading instruction at the collegiate level are recommended. Mutsaers (2020) explored whether a reader-centered approach—where instructors assume a facilitative role while students take greater ownership of textual interpretation—yielded stronger motivation than traditional methods. His findings indicated that this approach encouraged deeper student involvement, as they worked collaboratively to interpret texts rather than simply memorizing information.

Overall, integrating audiobooks into reading instruction appears to support learners' autonomy, intrinsic engagement, and persistence. This aligns with the premise that incorporating engaging and accessible learning tools, such as audiobooks, can enhance students' intrinsic motivation for reading while enriching their overall learning experience.

Table 3

Key Studies on Learning Motivation

Study	Focus	Key Findings
Deci & Ryan (1985)	Self-Determination Theory (SDT) in motivation	Differentiates between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, emphasizing the importance of autonomy in learning.
Eccles & Wigfield (2002)	Expectancy-Value Theory in reading motivation	Students are more likely to engage in reading if they perceive it as valuable and believe they can succeed.
Dörnyei (2005)	L2 Motivational Self System	Motivation in second language learning is influenced by personal aspirations and external obligations.
Divoll and	Impact of intrinsic motivation	Retention improves with intrinsic

Browning (2013)	on retention.	motivation strategies.
Chon (2017)	Extrinsic vs. intrinsic motivation in university students.	Extrinsic motivation often dominates; need to encourage intrinsic enjoyment.
Mutsaers (2020)	Reader-centered approach in motivating students.	Reader approach motivated students via group interpretations.
Kartal and Simsek (2017)	Audiobook benefits and continued usage intention.	Students found audiobooks beneficial and planned to continue usage.

Challenges in the Korean EFL Classroom

Korean university students face distinct challenges in EFL settings, particularly anxiety about pronunciation and hesitation to participate in oral discussions (Kim, 2019). These challenges are exacerbated by Korea’s highly competitive academic culture, especially at lower-ranked universities, where students encounter immense pressure to perform well (Manley, 2015). This pressure often leads to reluctance in group discussions and classroom participation. Manley suggests that providing students with ample processing time could foster greater willingness to engage in academic discussions.

Integrating audiobooks with reading could address this by giving students time to reflect on content, which may encourage participation and improve comprehension. This

aligns with Manley's (2015) research, which found that Korean students often hesitate to engage in group discussions due to academic pressure. Providing structured exposure through both listening and reading may reduce this anxiety by allowing students to process material in multiple ways, ultimately increasing their confidence in class participation.

Moreover, dual-modality input—through both reading and listening—has been shown to support deeper comprehension and vocabulary retention (Saito et al., 2023). This approach also supports Swallow's (2016) assertion that "students need to understand what they are reading as clearly as they know how to read it." The dual exposure to content through audiobooks and reading may help bridge the gap in understanding, alleviating anxiety and improving overall engagement in the learning process.

Conclusion

The literature reviewed reveals both the potential advantages of audiobooks and the complexities involved in their integration into EFL learning. While previous studies have explored various approaches to using audiobooks and reading, the question of how sequencing affects comprehension, spelling accuracy, and motivation remains underexplored. However, the specific effect of audiobook sequencing—whether students read before listening or listen before reading—remains underexplored, especially in Asian EFL contexts like South Korea.

This study aims to address this gap, focusing on Korean university students and their experiences with reading before listening and listening before reading. By examining how sequencing affects comprehension, spelling accuracy, and motivation, this research seeks to contribute meaningful insights into how audiobooks can be more strategically integrated into EFL instruction. The findings may inform pedagogical practices that better support learner needs in linguistically demanding and academically competitive environments.

Conceptual Framework

This study investigates how reading and listening sequencing affects reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and intrinsic motivation among Korean university EFL students. The independent variable, **audiobook sequencing**, interacts with three dependent variables: **reading comprehension**, **spelling accuracy**, and **intrinsic motivation to read**.

Two sequencing methods are assumed to have specific effects:

- **Reading before Listening (RBL):** In this condition, students first read the text, which is expected to enhance **spelling accuracy** by engaging them visually with the written form of words.
- **Listening before Reading (LBR):** Here, students listen to the audiobook before reading the text. This approach is anticipated to support **reading comprehension** by providing an auditory foundation that aids understanding of the material.

The dependent variables will be examined through a combination of comprehension tests, recall assessments, and motivational surveys.

Figure 1

Conceptual Framework

The study believes that the sequencing of audiobooks will have an effect on dependent variables. Specifically, the LBR method is expected to improve both reading comprehension and spelling accuracy due to initial exposure to the spoken language, enhancing understanding of vocabulary and sentence structures when students later read the text. Conversely, the RBL condition may lead to higher initial spelling accuracy as students engage directly with the written form. Both methods are also anticipated to affect intrinsic motivation to read differently; the LBR approach may enhance engagement by making the reading experience more accessible and enjoyable, while

the RBL method may foster motivation through a sense of achievement in recognizing and accurately spelling words.

Operational Use of Terms

Below are the operational definitions of the study's key terms, specifying how each variable will be measured and understood within this research.

- **Audiobook Sequencing:** The specific order in which students engage with text and its audiobook counterpart, comprising two conditions:
 - **Reading before Listening (RBL):** Students first read the text, followed by listening to the audiobook. This sequence is designed to focus on visual recognition of words to enhance initial spelling accuracy.
 - **Listening before Reading (LBR):** Students listen to the audiobook first, followed by reading. This sequence aims to improve comprehension by providing an auditory scaffold.
- **Reading Comprehension (RC):** The ability to understand, interpret, and analyze written content. This encompasses not only identifying key ideas, details, and themes within a text but also includes making inferences, synthesizing information, and critically evaluating the material. In this study, reading comprehension will be evaluated through comprehension tests that measure students' grasp of main ideas, supporting details, thematic elements, and their ability to draw conclusions and connections beyond the text.

- **Spelling Accuracy (SA):** The capability to recall and spell words encountered in reading and listening sessions accurately. Spelling accuracy is assessed using **short answer recall questions (SAQs)** that require students to reproduce specific terms from the text accurately in writing.
- **Intrinsic Motivation to Read (MTR):** The inner drive to engage with reading for personal enjoyment, interest, or satisfaction, independent of external rewards. Motivation is assessed through surveys that explore students' interest in reading activities, engagement levels, and willingness to read outside structured assignments.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research employed a multiple case study design to investigate the effects of audiobook sequencing on reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and intrinsic motivation among Korean university students. A multiple case study approach allows for a detailed, contextualized examination of individual participants, each considered a separate case (Stake, 1995; Merriam, 2009). In this study, the two audiobook sequencing strategies—Reading Before Listening (RBL) and Listening Before Reading (LBR)—formed the basis for cross-case comparison among three participants.

As Schoch (2020) notes, the multiple case study model facilitates richer insights into individual learning processes by comparing distinct learning experiences. This approach was particularly suited to the small sample size and the exploratory nature of the study, allowing for an in-depth understanding of how each sequencing method influenced participants' language learning outcomes.

The research followed a structured sequence of procedures, as illustrated in **Figure 2**. These included both quantitative and qualitative data collection measures:

Figure 2:

Research Process Flowchart

The study began with a **Pre-Survey** to gather initial insights into participants' backgrounds, reading habits, and motivational orientations. Throughout the intervention, students maintained a **Reading/Listening Log** to record their engagement with the materials. **Formative Assessments** evaluated comprehension and spelling at strategic points during each phase. After the second assessment of each phase, two **Group Discussions** were held—one after Chapters 1–12 and another after Chapters 13–27—to review and expand on the assessment results and to explore participants' reactions to the sequencing methods (RBL and LBR). Upon completing the entire intervention, participants completed a **Post-Survey** measuring perceived learning gains and

motivational changes. Finally, a **Guided Interview** was conducted to gain deeper individual insights into participants' overall experiences with the methods.

This design was informed by the piloting of the measures and materials, which included an early implementation with a comparable student group. Feedback from this process highlighted the importance of clearly structured pacing and meaningful engagement with both reading and listening materials. These insights guided the refinement of data collection tools, such as the spelling and comprehension assessments, and adjustments to the log format to better capture participant behavior.

This methodology also draws on theoretical frameworks discussed in Chapter 2, such as **Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985)** and **Expectancy-Value Theory (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002)**, both of which stress the significance of student perception and engagement in learning. These theories provided a rationale for exploring how audiobook sequencing might shape learners' motivation and reading behavior, especially in the context of Korea's exam-driven academic culture.

Participants

According to Stake (1995), a carefully chosen small sample in case study research enables rich, in-depth exploration of participants' experiences. Merriam (2009) also advocates for purposive sampling in qualitative research, arguing that selecting participants who meet particular criteria ensures the relevance and depth of findings. This study initially sought to examine four university students—two assigned to the Reading Before Listening (RBL) group and two to the Listening Before Reading (LBR)

group. Before Reading (LBR) group. However, one participant withdrew, resulting in a final sample of three students. This limitation is addressed further in the final chapter.

This sample size aligns with recommendations for multiple case studies, as Schoch (2020) notes that three to four participants provide an ideal range for managing depth and interpretability in qualitative research. Sleckar (2005) similarly highlights that small sample sizes in educational case studies yield meaningful qualitative insights while accommodating detailed interpretation of each participant's context and experience.

All participants were enrolled in a Practical English course at a Korean university. They were selected based on consistent class engagement, timely completion of assignments, and willingness to participate, to ensure minimal conflict with other academic responsibilities.

Participant Profiles

The final participant pool consisted of three Korean university students. Their academic majors were in **Nursing** and **Counseling Psychology**, offering some disciplinary variety. All were second year students and had intermediate-level English proficiency, as observed through classroom performance. While not representative of the entire student population, this group provided sufficient diversity to yield varied perspectives on audiobook sequencing.

Selection Criteria

The selection of participants was based on several criteria, each aimed at ensuring reliability and relevance to the research goals.

Course Background

Participants were enrolled in Practical English 1 and 2, which are required first-year university English courses. While both courses primarily emphasize speaking and listening, students occasionally engage in reading short passages, completing vocabulary-based tasks, or responding to comprehension questions related to textbook dialogues. These limited instances offer indirect opportunities to observe students' reading behavior and motivation. Practical English 2 serves as an extension of Practical English 1, using similar teaching and learning activities but introducing slightly more challenging content and discussion topics. Neither course, however, includes explicit instruction in reading comprehension, spelling, or motivational strategies.

Engagement in Class

Students were chosen based on their active class participation and regular completion of homework in their Practical English 2 in the fall 2024 semester. Those who frequently contributed to discussions and demonstrated consistent effort in the

class were prioritized, as this level of engagement suggested a higher likelihood of full participation in the study procedures.

Proficiency Levels

English proficiency was assessed by the researcher/professor based on students' performance and assignment completion within the Practical English 2 classes, which served as the context for gauging overall class engagement. The participants consistently demonstrated timely submission of assignments and showed eagerness to assist their classmates, reflecting their active involvement and satisfactory proficiency levels in the course.

While no standardized test was administered, classroom observations and performance on tasks by the researcher aligned with the course content offered a practical measure of ability. Kartal and Simsek (2017) support the use of classroom-based assessments for gauging proficiency, as they directly reflect students' functional language skills.

Prior Experience with RBL and LBR

None of the participants had prior experience specifically using audiobook sequencing strategies such as Reading Before Listening (RBL) or Listening Before Reading (LBR). However, all participants reported varying levels of familiarity and experience with audiobooks in general, ranging from occasional to frequent use. This was confirmed through the pre-survey and informal interviews. According to

Tusmagambet (2020), prior familiarity with these techniques can introduce bias, making it important to work with students unfamiliar with the sequencing formats.

Motivation

Motivation was initially gauged by observing voluntary participation in the Practical English 2 classes, where students demonstrated eagerness and consistent engagement without external incentives. This voluntary involvement suggested an intrinsic interest in English learning, aligning with the principles of Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Later, motivation was further confirmed through a pre-survey that included Likert-scale items measuring students' enjoyment of English reading and willingness to engage with audiobooks. Motivation was considered essential for sustaining effort throughout the multiple stages of the study.

Potential Selection Bias

It is important to acknowledge that selecting motivated and high-performing students may introduce selection bias. As Mook (1983) warns, such bias may limit the generalizability of findings. This study's primary goal, however, was not broad generalization but deep understanding of how audiobook sequencing affects language development among engaged learners. This trade-off was made intentionally to ensure the feasibility and integrity of the study given its qualitative, exploratory nature.

Locale and Context

This study was conducted at a private university in South Korea, where English instruction for non-English majors is structured around two mandatory foundation courses: *Practical English 1* and *Practical English 2*. These courses are typically taken by first-year students and run for 15 weeks per semester. The primary emphasis of both courses is on oral communication skills, including speaking fluency, listening comprehension, and conversational strategies. Instructional materials are typically sourced from major publishers such as Cambridge or Oxford, and the curriculum is largely centered on textbook-based dialogues, audio tracks, vocabulary practice, and pair/group speaking activities. While listening is practiced regularly, reading comprehension is not a central focus, and long-form reading materials—such as novels—are rarely incorporated into the course design.

Practical English 2 is essentially an extension of Practical English 1, with similar instructional goals and assessment methods. Both courses aim to improve students' communicative competence, though Practical English 2 may introduce slightly more advanced vocabulary and discussion topics. However, neither course explicitly targets reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, or reading motivation as core objectives. These areas are touched upon only indirectly, such as through textbook vocabulary sections or incidental reading exercises.

Drawing from my teaching experience at this institution, as well as consistent with established findings in the literature, many students exhibit a reluctance or anxiety when speaking English during class. This pattern of behavior is well-documented in

second language acquisition research, with several scholars (Dörnyei, 2014; Horwitz & Young, 1991; Horwitz, 2001; MacIntyre & Gardner, 1991) identifying language anxiety as a critical factor that inhibits learners' participation, performance, and willingness to communicate in the target language.

Given this affective barrier, the study explored the use of audiobook-based instruction as an alternative form of language engagement. By sequencing reading and listening tasks around a full-length young adult novel (*Animorphs*), the study sought to foster greater exposure to authentic English input in a low-stakes, immersive format. The goal was to reduce the pressure associated with oral performance while simultaneously supporting students' development in reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and motivation to read. This multimodal approach was designed to complement—but remain independent of—the existing curriculum, offering a richer and more personalized language learning experience without adding to students' classroom anxiety.

Data Collection and Tools

Data collection in this study employed a combination of quantitative and qualitative instruments: reading comprehension quizzes, spelling assessments, pre- and post-surveys, reading/listening logs, guided interviews, and group discussions. To streamline administration and ensure consistency, all instruments were administered via Google Forms, a platform familiar to the participants and well-suited for real-time, remote, and in-class data collection. This approach promoted convenience and

minimized technical difficulties, ensuring accurate, complete responses (Adelia et al., 2021).

All instruments were validated either through expert review or pilot testing under the guidance of a professor affiliated with the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU), under the authority of the Dean's office..

Instruments

Book and Audiobook: *Animorphs: The Invasion* (1996) by K.A. Applegate

Rationale for Selection:

Animorphs: The Invasion (1996) by K.A. Applegate was selected for several reasons. First, both the book (available as a free PDF of approximately 100 pages) and the audiobook (offered free by R3 Shorts, 2018) were easily accessible for participants. The novel had been successfully used in a prior pilot study, providing a tested basis for its suitability. Importantly, the length and difficulty of the text were appropriate for EFL learners at the university level. Tsai (2012) highlights that the length of reading materials should be manageable to allow students to complete them within the course timeframe, which supports maintaining learner motivation and effective engagement. In line with this, *Animorphs* was selected to ensure that participants could realistically finish both the book and audiobook within the one-month intervention period, making it feasible for the study's schedule and objectives.

Book Summary:

Animorphs: The Invasion (1996) is the first installment in K.A. Applegate's acclaimed young adult science fiction series. The novel follows five teenagers—Jake, Rachel, Cassie, Tobias, and Marco—who encounter a dying alien called an Andalite. Before his death, the Andalite warns them of a secret invasion by the Yeerks, a parasitic alien species that takes control of human hosts. He grants the teens the power to morph into animals they touch, making them the only resistance against the hidden invasion. The story explores themes of identity, courage, and moral responsibility, all delivered in clear, accessible language and fast-paced storytelling.

Pedagogical Justification:

Reading full-length English texts can be especially challenging for Korean learners (Bolton et al., 2022). Young Adult (YA) literature such as *Animorphs* offers a more accessible entry point (Yassin & Saed, 2021), particularly due to its relatable themes and moderate difficulty level. As Day and Bamford (1998) and Tsai (2012) emphasize, engaging narratives that maintain a balance between linguistic challenge and reader interest are highly effective in promoting extensive reading. This book's narrative structure, action-oriented plot, and accessible vocabulary made it particularly suitable for sustained reading and listening in this study.

Reading Comprehension Quizzes

Description:

The comprehension quizzes consisted of short-answer questions (SAQs) designed to assess both literal and inferential understanding of *Animorphs: The*

Invasion. SAQs were selected over multiple-choice questions (MCQs) to discourage guessing—a common issue with MCQs—and to promote deeper cognitive engagement (Budiyono, 2018; Ko, 2010; Ozuru et al., 2017).

Rationale and Adaptation:

The shift from MCQs to SAQs reflects the results of a pilot study in which participants frequently guessed answers. SAQs required students to articulate their understanding in their own words, promoting critical thinking and authentic comprehension. (Budiyono, 2018; Ko, 2010; Ozuru et al., 2017)

Question Diversity:

Based on expert feedback, the revised quizzes incorporated literal, inferential, and evaluative questions, ensuring a well-rounded assessment of comprehension skills. Originally the quizzes contained 49 literal-only questions for Chapters 1-12 and 31 literal-only questions for Chapters 13-27. These early versions lacked opportunities to assess higher-order thinking. After validation, the quizzes were revised to include 28 literal , 10 inferential, and 7 evaluative questions for each half of the book. This restructuring allowed for a more balanced coverage of Bloom’s taxonomy across the comprehension spectrum.

A summary of the revisions is presented below

Table 4:

Quiz Composition Before and After Validation

Chapters	Literal (Original)	Literal (Revised)	Inferential	Evaluative	Total (Revised)
1-12	49	28	10	7	45
13-27	31	28	10	7	45

Validation:

A validated version of the quizzes was refined through expert input and piloted with a small group. All instruments were reviewed under the authority of the Dean's Office in coordination with a UPOU-affiliated professor. Based on validator recommendations, the original quizzes—focused mainly on literal comprehension—were revised to include literal, inferential, and evaluative questions, promoting higher-order thinking and a more comprehensive assessment of comprehension skills. Additionally, clear instructions were added to guide students through the quizzes, addressing the validator's suggestion to deepen the assessment with higher-order questions. These revisions were made accordingly to enhance clarity and alignment with research objectives (see Appendix D).

Methodology and Rationale:

Spelling was assessed indirectly through students' written responses to comprehension questions rather than a standalone spelling test. This approach is

supported by Tsai (2012), who argues that spelling proficiency can be meaningfully evaluated in context. This method allowed for natural assessment of both comprehension and spelling, ensuring authenticity.

Word Selection and Complexity:

Target vocabulary was drawn directly from the book and audiobook to ensure contextual relevance. Words were selected based on their frequency and narrative significance, reflecting research that repeated exposure in meaningful contexts improves retention and recall (Nation, 2001). Complexity was carefully aligned to students' English proficiency levels to support fairness and validity. This alignment reflects the Zone of Proximal Development theory (Vygotsky, 1978), which emphasizes learning within a suitable challenge range. Vocabulary was reinforced through student-generated logs completed after each quiz, ensuring engagement with and understanding of the target words before assessment. While literal comprehension questions typically prompted single-word or short responses, inferential and evaluative items required students to use key vocabulary in meaningful phrases—such as “Tobias soared on the thermals”—thereby demonstrating both correct spelling and comprehension. To promote authentic recall and reduce rote memorization, students were not told in advance which words would be evaluated, consistent with findings that advanced knowledge of test items can inflate vocabulary scores (Laufer & Goldstein, 2004).

Presentation of Target Words:

Target words were assessed in the same form and context as encountered in the

book and audiobook. Students were not told which words would be evaluated, ensuring authentic recall. Spelling accuracy was measured through written responses—while literal questions often elicited single-word or short responses, inferential and evaluative questions required students to use vocabulary in meaningful phrases, demonstrating both spelling and comprehension.

Technology Bias Mitigation:

To prevent digital spell-check interference, in-class assessments were completed using devices with autocorrect and predictive text features disabled. Google Form settings were customized accordingly, and instructions clearly emphasized that responses should reflect unaided spelling ability.

Validation:

All quiz instruments were piloted, refined based on expert feedback, and validated through the UPOU Dean's Office in coordination with language education professionals.

The validator recommended clarifying the indirect nature of the spelling assessment, refining the vocabulary selection process, and aligning word complexity with students' proficiency levels. These suggestions were fully implemented in the final design.

Pre-Survey and Post-Survey

Methodology

Pre- Survey: Quantitative (Likert- Scale):

Adapted from Tsai (2012) and Wagar (2016), the pre- survey included demographic questions (year in university, major, prior audiobook use) followed by 27 Likert- scale items (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree) spanning four domains:

- **General English Proficiency** (e.g., “I find it easy to understand the main ideas in English texts.”; “I feel confident spelling most English words correctly.”)
- **Reading Comprehension Baseline** (e.g., “I have difficulty understanding complex vocabulary in English texts.”)
- **Spelling Confidence** (e.g., “I pay attention to spelling when I read English texts.”)
- **Intrinsic Motivation & Habits** (e.g., “I enjoy listening to audiobooks for fun.”; “I read for at least 30 minutes a day.”)

Post- Survey: Qualitative (Open- Ended Only):

Based on Turker (2010), restructured into **8 open- ended questions** prompting reflections on:

- Preferences between RBL and LBR
- Challenges and strategies
- Changes in Motivation and habits
- Perceived impact on comprehension and spelling

Rationale

- Quantitative pre- survey data provide a clear baseline against which sequencing effects can be measured, addressing validator concerns about establishing students' initial proficiency and attitudes (Joshi, Kale, Chandel, & Pal, 2015).
- Open- ended post- survey responses capture nuanced student experiences that closed items cannot, allowing exploration of emerging themes and personal insights into RBL and LBR methods (Patton, 2002).

Validation

Reviewed and approved under the authority of the Dean's Office at the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU).

- **Validator Feedback & Actions Taken:**
 - Omitted vague items (e.g., "My English is good.") to reduce ambiguity.
 - Justified and aligned item complexity by indicating participant proficiency levels (C1 and below) in the methodology.
 - Added 3–5 targeted items for each pre- survey domain (proficiency, comprehension, spelling, motivation) to enrich baseline data.
 - Redesigned the post- survey into an open- ended format to ensure depth of reflection without redundancy with quantitative measures.

All survey instruments were piloted with a small cohort to ensure clarity and relevance before final validation.

Reading and Listening Logs

Methodology & Structure:

- Participants completed a log after each chapter session (27 in total), recording:
 - Time spent reading (in minutes)
 - Number of times read and number of times listened
 - Listening speed used (e.g., normal, 1.25x)
 - Number and duration of pauses during listening
 - Four open- ended reflections (3–5 sentences each)
 - Difficult words encountered
 - Logs were submitted via Google Classroom on Google Docs, allowing the researcher to track entries in real time.

Reflection Prompts (per validator feedback):

1. What did you find most challenging in today's reading/listening?
2. How did you approach understanding the main ideas?
3. Which new or difficult words did you encounter, and how did you try to remember their spelling?
4. What part of today's material did you find most interesting, and why?

Rationale

Reading and listening logs promote metacognition and consistent engagement (Madjdi et al., 2024; Intasuk, 2024) and facilitate comparative analysis of reading vs.

listening habits (Friedland et al., 2017; Lee & Cha, 2020), building on Yeganeh's (2013) insights into timed repeated readings.

Validation:

Log templates were reviewed and piloted with a small student cohort, then approved and validated under the authority of the Dean's Office at the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU). Validator recommendations—to enrich logs with qualitative prompts and specify count and length—were fully implemented (see Appendix E).

Group Discussions

Format and Objectives

The group discussions were conducted after the second round of quizzes and lasted approximately 30 minutes per session. These semi-structured discussions were designed to reinforce students' engagement with the novel through collaborative review and deeper analysis. Each session began with a collective review of literal and inferential quiz questions, especially those that students had answered incorrectly. The researcher facilitated these discussions by prompting students to justify their answers, address misunderstandings, and work through the reasoning behind alternative responses. Once quiz content had been addressed, the discussion shifted to open-ended, evaluative prompts that invited students to explore character motivations, plot development, and thematic elements.

Rationale

The purpose of the group discussions was twofold: to enhance comprehension and to cultivate critical engagement with the text. This approach was grounded in Vygotsky's (1978) sociocultural theory, which posits that learning occurs through meaningful social interaction within the learner's *Zone of Proximal Development* (ZPD). By verbalizing their thoughts, questioning peers, and revising their interpretations collaboratively, students could bridge gaps in their understanding with guidance from both the researcher and one another. This peer-supported interaction provided opportunities for scaffolding, enabling learners to internalize new knowledge and perspectives. As Moge (2023) also argues, collaborative discourse is a powerful means of promoting deeper reading comprehension and critical thinking, particularly in EFL contexts. The researcher intentionally guided discussions on incorrect quiz responses, using oral dialogue as a formative tool to confirm understanding and reinforce language development.

Validation

The discussion prompts were developed in alignment with the study's research questions and refined after review by expert validators under the supervision of the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU) Dean's Office. The validation emphasized the importance of grounding the prompts in operational definitions and ensuring alignment with other instruments, such as the quizzes and surveys. Revisions focused on improving the balance between structured comprehension checks and open-ended prompts, allowing for both consistency and adaptability during sessions.

Guided Interviews

Format and Objective

The individual guided interviews were conducted on the final day of the study. These interviews followed a semi-structured format, drawing on the interview guide approach (Patton, 2002) to allow both consistency and flexibility. The questions were directly derived from the post-survey, which students had already completed. During the interview, each survey item was reviewed one by one, with students prompted to explain their responses, clarify meanings, and provide concrete examples. Additional time was spent reviewing quiz questions that had previously posed difficulty, with the researcher confirming comprehension through targeted oral questioning and scaffolding.

Depth and Reflexivity

These interviews provided a crucial opportunity for students to reflect on their experiences with both the Reading Before Listening (RBL) and Listening Before Reading (LBR) methods. Students shared their evolving reading and listening strategies, learning preferences, and motivation levels. The format allowed themes from the post-survey to be expanded into richer, more personalized narratives. Through this one-on-one dialogue, the researcher could explore patterns of learning and retention not captured through other tools. Consistent with Vygotsky's (1978) emphasis on the dialogic construction of knowledge, the interviews functioned as a scaffolded space in which students could express, negotiate, and clarify their learning.

Validation

As with the group discussions, the interview guide was validated and revised with feedback from an expert and endorsed by the UPOU Dean's Office. The final guide ensured alignment with the study's conceptual framework and research objectives. All interviews were recorded, transcribed, and anonymized to protect participants' confidentiality. Thematic analysis was used to interpret the data, providing a qualitative foundation for triangulating survey and quiz results.

Instrument Validation and Revisions

All research instruments—including quizzes, surveys, logs, and interview guides—were reviewed by a validator affiliated with the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU) Dean's Office to ensure clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study's research objectives. Table 5 presents a summary of the validator's feedback and the corresponding revisions made to the research instruments.

Table 5:

Summary of Validator Feedback and Action Taken

Area	Validator Comment	Action Taken
Participant Selection	Clarify selection criteria and potential bias	Selection criteria were revised to emphasize participant diligence and engagement; selection bias was acknowledged in the study limitations.
RBL/LBR Procedures	Add detailed administration steps	A new section was added outlining the sequencing

		steps, material distribution, and participant instructions.
Quiz Content	Include higher-order questions	Short-answer questions (SAQs) were revised to incorporate inferential and evaluative items.
Spelling Assessment	Clarify indirect assessment approach	Additional explanation was provided, and vocabulary complexity was aligned with participant proficiency levels.
Surveys	Remove vague items; align with domains	Survey items were revised for clarity, and Likert-scale questions were expanded to cover each domain more comprehensively.
Logs	Enrich reflection prompts	Four open-ended reflection prompts were added to each log entry to encourage deeper participant insights.
Interviews	Ensure alignment with post-survey themes	The interview guide was restructured around post-survey themes and quiz content to improve consistency and relevance.

These revisions enhanced the reliability of the instruments and ensured their alignment with the study’s overall goals.

RBL and LBR Administration

To ensure structured exposure to the material, participants in both groups followed a controlled sequence of reading and listening activities. The study

implemented a two-phase approach, allowing each group to experience both Reading Before Listening (RBL) and Listening Before Reading (LBR) conditions.

At the beginning of the study, participants received explicit instructions outlining their assigned sequence. The RBL group was provided with the assigned book chapters in written form at the start of each study week. They were required to read the assigned material within a one-week period, logging their daily reading progress. After completing the first phase of reading, they then received the corresponding audiobook files, which they listened to over the following week.

The LBR group followed the reverse sequence. They received the assigned audiobook chapters first, listening to them daily for one week while documenting their engagement in listening logs. After completing the listening phase, they then were given the corresponding written text to read over the next week, similarly recording their reading activity.

At the end of Week 1, all participants took a formative assessment to evaluate their comprehension and retention of the material covered in their assigned mode (either reading or listening). After transitioning to their second condition, they retook the same assessment at the end of Week 2, allowing for a comparative analysis of their performance across the two sequencing conditions.

Additionally, group discussions were conducted at the end of the first set of assigned RBL and LBR chapters, providing participants with an opportunity to reflect on their experiences and discuss their engagement with the material. A final group discussion took place in the last week after participants have completed the second phase, allowing for a more comprehensive summative reflection on their overall experiences with both sequencing conditions.

To maintain consistency and prevent deviation from the assigned sequence, participants were explicitly instructed not to read or listen beyond their assigned materials during each phase. After completing their first assigned mode, they switched conditions: RBL participants transitioned to LBR, and LBR participants transitioned to RBL.

This approach was designed to ensure comparable exposure time for both groups, with each participant engaging with the text and audio components for equal durations. The use of daily reading and listening logs provided a structured record of participant engagement, ensuring adherence to the assigned sequence. The inclusion of formative assessments and group discussions enhanced the depth of qualitative insights while allowing for measurable comparisons between the two sequencing methods. By controlling for sequence, duration, and engagement, this methodology strengthened the replicability of the study and provided meaningful insights into the effects of audiobook sequencing in EFL contexts.

Timeline

Week 1

- Orientation and vocabulary review.
- Pre-survey
- Begin Reading Before Listening (RBL) and Listening Before Reading (LBR) for chapters 1-12.

Week 2

- Administer the first comprehension quiz.
- Collect reading and listening logs.
- Groups either read or listen.

Week 3

- Administer the first comprehension quiz again.
- Continue collecting logs.
- Group discussion of chapters 1-12.
- Switch groups between RBL and LBR.
- Begin chapters 13-27.

Week 4

- Administer the second comprehension quiz.
- Switch between listening and reading.

Week 5

- Administer the second comprehension quiz again.
- Group discussion of chapters 13-27.

Week 6

- Conduct post-test (survey).

Week 7

- Hold individual interviews based on the post-survey

Table 6:

Research Schedule

Week/Activities	RBL	LBR
Week 1 Orientation Presurvey Vocab Review	Both	Both
Week 1 Start reading/listening Chapter 1-12. Read/Listen for Homework	Group 1- read	Group 2-listen
Week 2 Quiz 1 Take 1	Both	Both
Week 2 Chapters 1-12	Group 1-listen	Group 2 - read
Week 3 Quiz 1 Take 2	Both	Both
Week 3	Both	Both

Group Discussion 1-12		
Week 4 Change roles Chapters 13-27	Group 2	Group 1
Week 4 Quiz 2 Take 1	Both	Both
Week 5 Chapters 13-27	Group 2-listen	Group 1-Read
Week 5 Quiz 2 Take 2 Group Discussion 13-27	Both	Both
Week 6 Post-Survey	Both	Both
Week 7	Both	Both

Follow-up Individual Interviews		
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Data Analysis

This study adopted a mixed-methods analytical approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative data to investigate the effects of audiobook sequencing methods—Reading-Before-Listening (RBL) and Listening-Before-Reading (LBR)—on Korean EFL students' reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and motivation to read. Given the small sample size ($N = 3$), manual coding was employed to enable close, context-sensitive engagement with participant responses (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Yin, 2018).

The analysis employed an integration method combining quantitative and qualitative findings to achieve a comprehensive understanding of audiobook sequencing effects. This involved triangulation, where insights from guided interviews and group discussions were compared with quantitative data from surveys and assessments (Yin, 2018).

Manual coding was chosen due to the study's scale and context. Creswell and Poth (2018) emphasize that manual coding is appropriate for qualitative studies with small samples, allowing close researcher engagement and context-sensitive judgment. Yin (2018) supports manual analysis in case studies, highlighting the richness of case-based evidence best interpreted through direct engagement and data comparison.

By employing side-by-side comparison, qualitative themes identified in discussions and interviews were supported with statistical trends from quantitative data. This approach enabled a nuanced interpretation of how participants' experiences align with or diverge from numerical results, enriching understanding of RBL and LBR effectiveness.

Quantitative Analysis

Two primary types of quantitative data were examined: comprehension quiz scores and spelling accuracy, both drawn from student performance during the two phases of the study (sequencing switch).

- **Comprehension Quizzes:** These consisted of chapter-specific questions administered after each study phase. Scores were manually tabulated and descriptively analyzed across both phases and between the RBL and LBR groups. Patterns such as improvement, decline, or stability were noted. Given the case study's small sample size (N=3), inferential statistics were not employed, aligning with recommendations by Merriam (2009) and Yin (2018) to prioritize context-based interpretation over generalization.
- **Spelling Accuracy:** Spelling errors in short-answer quiz responses were manually counted and documented. Frequencies were analyzed across study phases and sequencing conditions to determine whether sequencing influenced spelling development over time. Manual error coding is considered valid for small-scale educational studies when investigating language accuracy in authentic, contextualized tasks (Miles, Huberman, & Saldaña, 2014).

Qualitative Analysis

Qualitative data included open-ended post-survey responses, guided interviews, group discussions, and informal reading logs. These were examined using thematic analysis, following a six-step manual coding procedure modeled after Tesch's (1990) coding framework (as cited in Creswell & Poth, 2018) and Braun and Clarke's (2006) approach. The following steps were undertaken:

1. Familiarization with the Data

All qualitative responses from surveys, interviews, discussions, and logs were read multiple times to develop an initial understanding. Marginal notes and early reflections were recorded to capture first impressions and recurrent ideas (Creswell & Poth, 2018). For example, early notes highlighted that students often described re-listening or pausing audio, which later emerged as significant codes.

2. Initial Coding

Each data source was manually coded using both deductive and inductive approaches. Deductive codes were drawn from the research questions (e.g., reading comprehension, motivation to read, spelling accuracy), while inductive codes emerged from participants' responses (e.g., relistening as a strategy, pausing audio for unknown words).

Three coding techniques were applied to enhance analytical depth and clarity (Miles, Huberman, & Saldaña, 2014):

- **Attribute Coding:** Used to capture participant-specific characteristics, such as major, number of years studying English, initial sequencing group, or changes in reading behavior and to compare patterns across these groups. For example, Student 2 (initial LBR) showed increased listening engagement post-switch, listening more frequently and pausing more often for clarification.
- **Simultaneous Coding:** Applied when single statements reflected multiple ideas. For instance, a student’s log showed that they read a chapter multiple times for comprehension and also listened to the same chapter several times. This entry was coded under engagement, motivation, and comprehension. Notably, this student also demonstrated an increase in test scores following this pattern of repeated exposure, suggesting a link between these overlapping behaviors and improved performance.
- **Pattern Coding:** Employed to group similar codes under broader interpretive categories, helping identify causal trends and perceived effects of sequencing. Before coding, “self-regulated learning” was defined as learners’ capacity to plan, monitor, and evaluate their own learning processes (Zimmerman, 2002). One pattern code under this theme, included repeated strategies such as rereading chapters, relistening, pausing, and adjusting playback speed to support comprehension. These behaviors reflect students’ ability to monitor, control, and direct their own learning processes—hallmarks of self-regulated learning (Zimmerman, 2002). In addition to behavioral data, pattern coding was also used to identify commonly missed or consistently correct quiz questions across participants, revealing shared areas of difficulty or mastery. These question-level

patterns offered insight into which aspects of the text posed comprehension or vocabulary challenges, regardless of sequencing conditions.

The coding process followed Tesch's (1990) steps for open-ended qualitative data (as cited in Creswell & Poth, 2018), which involve identifying key segments of text, assigning preliminary codes, and grouping them into meaningful categories. Behavioral indicators such as the number of reading/listening sessions, duration of study time, playback speed adjustments, and frequency of pauses were also coded to assess student engagement and metacognitive strategies.

3. Theme Development

Related codes were grouped into broader themes. For instance, codes such as "pausing audio," "re-reading chapters," and "listening repeatedly" were organized under the overarching theme of self-regulated learning strategies, which involve learners' ability to actively monitor, control, and reflect on their cognitive and motivational processes during learning (Zimmerman, 2002). This step was guided by Braun and Clarke's (2006) processes of searching for and reviewing themes, which emphasize organizing related codes into higher-order thematic categories.

4. Triangulation with Quantitative Data

Emerging qualitative themes were triangulated with quantitative results and formative assessment data from quizzes testing comprehension and spelling accuracy. For instance, Student 2 (initial LBR) reported listening to and reading chapters more than once to improve understanding. This behavior coincided with

a noticeable increase in their score on the second quiz during the first phase of the study. Students 2 and 3, who reported rereading chapters or relistening during the second phase after switching to RBL, often showed gains in comprehension and spelling, revealing a potential link between self-regulated learning behaviors (Zimmerman, 2002) and performance. Triangulation allowed for convergence or divergence between students' reported experiences and their assessed outcomes, increasing the credibility and depth of findings (Yin, 2018; Patton, 1999).

5. Group Discussions and Member Checking

Member checking was primarily conducted through group discussions and follow-up guided interviews, which followed the post-survey questions to allow students to expand on their responses. Member checking, a process by which participants review and confirm the accuracy of the data and interpretations, is widely recognized as a critical technique to enhance the credibility and trustworthiness of qualitative research findings (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Creswell & Poth, 2018). During these sessions, students were invited to reflect on their quiz results, learning strategies, and perceived progress. These interactive conversations enabled participants to confirm, clarify, or elaborate on their earlier input, thereby enhancing the accuracy and trustworthiness of the interpretations (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Creswell & Poth, 2018). While post-survey and pre-survey responses supplemented these discussions, the most impactful insights arose from this dialogic engagement with the participants. This process strengthened

the study's credibility by ensuring alignment between researcher interpretations and students' own perspectives (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Creswell & Poth, 2018).

6. Reflexivity and Interpretation

Throughout the analysis, the researcher kept analytic memos to track interpretive decisions and personal reflections. Given the researcher's dual role as both instructor and analyst, reflexivity was especially important to acknowledge potential biases and power dynamics inherent in this insider position (Finlay, 2002). Steps were taken to minimize subjectivity and ensure interpretative rigor through ongoing reflection, memoing, and peer debriefing (Tracy, 2010; Creswell & Poth, 2018).

Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The final stage of analysis involved comparing and integrating both data types to generate a more comprehensive view of how audiobook sequencing impacted students. For example, students who demonstrated improved spelling accuracy during the RBL phase often reported greater attention to written forms and spelling patterns. Conversely, students who showed higher comprehension during the LBR phase commonly described using listening to scaffold unfamiliar vocabulary and overall meaning. This alignment of numerical data with self-reported experiences added interpretive depth and contextual clarity to the findings (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017; Yin, 2018).

Justification for Manual Analysis

Manual coding was intentionally chosen for this small- scale qualitative case study. This approach enabled deep, context- sensitive interaction with rich narrative data and allowed the researcher to apply nuanced judgment throughout analysis (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Although manual methods can introduce subjectivity and limit replicability compared to software- assisted coding, rigorous measures—including triangulation, member checking, and reflexive memoing—were implemented to mitigate bias and enhance the study’s credibility and trustworthiness (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Yin, 2018).

Limitations

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting its findings:

1. **Sample Size:** The small sample size of participants limits the generalizability of the study’s findings. With only a few participants involved in each group, the results may not fully reflect the experiences or outcomes of a broader population of university EFL students. This limitation may affect the ability to draw definitive conclusions about the effects of RBL and LBR methods. However, Slecker (2005) argues that small sample sizes can still contribute meaningful insights to research and data.
2. **Research Duration:** The relatively short duration of the study, spanning only a few weeks, may not capture the long-term effects of the RBL and LBR methods on reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and motivation. A longer study

period could provide more insight into how these methods influence language acquisition over time, highlighting the realistic time constraints faced by participants.

3. **Participant Time Constraints:** Many potential participants are university students with busy academic schedules, which may limit their time and commitment to engage fully in the reading and listening activities. Their other academic responsibilities could influence the time they dedicate to the study's tasks, potentially affecting their performance and the overall outcomes..
4. **Data Collection Tools:** The study relied on surveys and quizzes for data collection, including pre- and post-tests that depend on self-reported responses. The open-ended nature of the post-survey allowed participants to express their feelings in detail, but it can be time-consuming and subject to bias (Hyman & Sierra, 2016). In contrast, the pre-survey's close-ended format was easier for participants to complete, though it limited their ability to provide in-depth responses (Hyman & Sierra, 2016).
5. **Context-Specific Nature:** As the study was conducted at a specific private university in South Korea, the findings may be context-specific and not fully applicable to other educational environments or EFL learners outside this setting.

Ethical Considerations

This study ensured that all participants gave their informed consent before participating. Consent forms were provided, clearly outlining the study's purpose, procedures, and any potential risks or benefits involved. Participants were informed of

their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. To maintain anonymity, all personal information was kept confidential, and pseudonyms were used in any reports or publications. Data collected was securely stored, and only the researcher had access to it, ensuring the privacy and integrity of the information throughout the research process.

CHAPTER 4:

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Introduction

This chapter presents the results of the study, which examined the effects of audiobook sequencing—Reading Before Listening (RBL) and Listening Before Reading (LBR)—on the reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and reading motivation of three Korean university EFL students. Participants read a full-length novel (*Animorphs*) and listened to the corresponding audiobook in two sequential phases, switching methods halfway through.

The primary objective of this chapter is to answer the following research questions:

1. **What is the effect of RBL on selected university EFL students’**
 - a. reading comprehension?
 - b. spelling?
 - c. intrinsic motivation to read?

2. **What is the effect of LBR on selected university EFL students’**

- a. reading comprehension?
- b. spelling?
- c. intrinsic motivation to read?

Each student began with either RBL or LBR and then switched sequencing methods after Chapter 12, allowing within-participant comparisons over time. One participant withdrew early, leaving three complete cases. Despite being a small sample, meaningful quantitative data (short-answer quizzes, pre- and post-surveys, reading/listening logs) and qualitative reflections (guided interviews, group discussions) was collected. Detailed results of the pre-survey and post-survey are provided in Appendices F and G, respectively; student reading/listening logs are in Appendix H; and full quiz answer sheets are in Appendix I.

Summary of Participants

All three final participants met the selection criteria described in Chapter 3: they were Korean university students enrolled in Practical English courses, had over 10 years of English study experience, and were able to complete both reading and listening tasks over the four-week period.

- **Student 1 (S1)** was a third-year Counseling Psychology major with extensive experience reading English novels and listening to audiobooks, expressing high confidence in English reading and listening.

- **Student 2 (S2)** was a second-year Counseling Psychology major who found listening easier than reading before the study but expressed a preference for reading during the study.
- **Student 3 (S3)** was a second-year Nursing major with moderate confidence in reading and listening, but limited prior audiobook experience.

They demonstrated varying degrees of prior audiobook exposure, from high to low, which provided a useful contrast for analyzing engagement patterns. Their demographic and linguistic backgrounds aligned well with the selection criteria detailed in Chapter 3, ensuring the study's exploratory focus on diverse learner profiles within the EFL university context.

On the Group Discussion Findings

Group discussions were intended to complement the quantitative and individual qualitative data but were not analyzed as a standalone data source due to limited participation and time constraints. Instead, relevant comments, reactions, and behaviors observed during group discussions were incorporated within the case analyses. This approach allowed for a richer understanding of participants' subjective experiences with audiobook sequencing, particularly their struggles and preferences related to reading comprehension and spelling accuracy. These qualitative insights helped reinforce and explain the quantitative outcomes observed in quiz results and reading-listening logs.

For example, S2's hesitation and fear of mistakes during the LBR phase were evident in group discussions, supporting quantitative findings. Similarly, S3's

appreciation of peer explanations in group discussions highlighted the social support that aided comprehension.

The Case of Student 1 (S1)

Linguistic and reading background and experience before the study

S1 was a third-year university student majoring in Counseling Psychology who had studied English for over 10 years. Based on pre-survey responses (see Appendix F for full instrument and results), S1 was highly confident in using English, particularly in receptive skills such as reading and listening. S1 also reported frequent use of audiobooks both inside and outside the classroom and expressed enjoyment of reading English novels. This familiarity with audiobooks and positive attitude towards English reading provided a strong foundation for engaging with the study tasks.

Performance and participation during the study

S1 began the study by reading the first twelve chapters of the novel following the Reading Before Listening (RBL) sequence, then switched to Listening Before Reading (LBR) for the remaining chapters. Regarding preference, S1 stated, “After listening first, I felt I could imagine more without focusing on reading,” indicating a stronger connection with the LBR phase. Overall, S1 expressed a preference for the LBR approach, suggesting that listening before reading helped improve visualization and engagement with the story.

S1 demonstrated improved comprehension scores in both RBL and LBR phases. However, the nature of these improvements differed. The RBL phase appeared to strengthen literal comprehension and recall by providing visual and textual familiarity, while the LBR phase fostered enhanced mental imagery and emotional engagement with the story. S1's reflections indicated that listening before reading helped create vivid mental pictures that deepened understanding, supporting findings from previous studies highlighting the benefits of auditory input in building mental representations (Chang, 2011). Thus, while both sequences contributed positively, the LBR method uniquely supported affective and imaginative comprehension processes.

Spelling accuracy for S1 revealed some challenges during the RBL phase, with most errors related to proper nouns such as "Andalites," "Tovias," "Casie," and "Jack." However, after switching to the LBR phase, S1 demonstrated near-perfect spelling of proper nouns. Vocabulary spelling also improved, with corrections such as "tale" to "tail" and "gorila" to "gorilla" after reading, indicating that visual exposure remains crucial for accurate orthographic knowledge despite the benefits of listening.

Time spent reading per chapter decreased slightly from 7–11 minutes in the RBL phase to 5–10 minutes in the LBR phase, possibly reflecting increased fluency and comfort with the text. As S1 already noted, "After listening first, I felt I could imagine more without focusing on reading."

In the guided interview, S1 explained that "hearing the intonations and emotion first helped to understand what the character was feeling before seeing the words,"

emphasizing tone guided comprehension. This reaction supports findings from Saito et al. (2023) about the emotional engagement facilitated by oral input.

Effects on motivation to read using audiobooks and following RBL and LBR

Kartal and Simsek (2017) found that students perceived audiobooks as beneficial and expressed a strong intention to continue using them. This aligns well with the effects observed in this study regarding motivation to read when using different audiobook sequencing methods.

In the post-survey (see Appendix G), Student 1 (S1) clearly indicated a preference for the Listening Before Reading (LBR) sequence, noting that listening first enhanced imagination and engagement with the story. Although S1 acknowledged that reading first (RBL) helped with recalling character names more easily, overall motivation and enjoyment of reading increased during the LBR phase. These findings support Eccles and Wigfield's (2002) motivation theory and Kartal and Simsek's (2017) work, emphasizing how an increased emotional connection and a sense of competence can contribute to sustained reading interest.

The Case of Student 2 (S2)

Linguistic and reading background and experience before the study

S2 was a second-year university student majoring in Counseling Psychology who has studied English for over 10 years. S2 did not express a particular preference for

reading or listening, indicating a neutral attitude toward various English texts. However, prior to the study, S2 reported finding listening easier than reading, reflecting a different learning style compared to S1.

Performance and participation during the study

S2 began the study following the Listening Before Reading (LBR) sequence for the first twelve chapters, then switched to Reading Before Listening (RBL) for the remaining chapters. Regarding motivation and engagement, S2 reported, “Reading is easier for me to follow. The audiobook was fast,” indicating a preference for the RBL phase despite initially finding listening easier. This supports Vandergriff’s (2007) finding that L2 learners may struggle with native-speed audio due to increased cognitive load, whereas reading enables them to self-regulate their pace for better comprehension.

Spelling accuracy during the LBR phase appeared stronger than it actually was, primarily because several items were left unanswered rather than answered incorrectly. This hesitation may have stemmed from a fear of making mistakes or being evaluated negatively, a response documented in active education contexts (Downing et al., 2020). After switching to the RBL phase, spelling accuracy improved markedly, highlighting the importance of visual input in reinforcing orthographic knowledge (Al-Jarf, 2005).

In terms of reading comprehension, S2’s quiz scores indicated steady but modest improvements during the RBL phase, while the LBR phase showed less consistent gains. This aligns with S2’s expressed preference for reading as the primary method of engagement.

S2's reading and listening logs demonstrated consistent diligence across both phases. During the RBL phase, the student typically read each chapter 2–3 times, spending between 8 and 14 minutes per chapter. In the earlier LBR phase, the student also read each chapter twice and listened to it approximately 2–3 times on average, usually at regular speed. Despite this consistent engagement, comprehension scores were lower during the LBR phase, suggesting that the sequence of listening before reading may have influenced understanding. This data supports the conclusion that visual scaffolding had a more substantial impact on this learner's performance.

Data from group discussions and guided interviews indicated that S2 felt “more sure of [the] answers when [they] read first,” suggesting increased confidence and emotional comfort during the RBL phase. In contrast, S2 expressed greater hesitancy and a fear of making mistakes during the LBR phase, which may have hindered engagement and comprehension. This supports findings by Downing et al. (2003), who argue that perceived competence and emotional security are essential for deeper learning and motivation.

Effects on motivation to read using audiobooks and following RBL and LBR

S2's survey responses and guided interview reflections indicated a clear increase in motivation to read when following the RBL method. S2 explained that reading first offered more control over pacing and comprehension, while listening required sustained concentration and faster mental processing. Although S2 did not dislike audiobooks, they found that reading before listening led to better focus, deeper understanding, and

stronger recall. Group discussion transcripts further supported this shift: after switching from LBR to RBL, S2 showed greater confidence, engagement, and overall enjoyment with the material.

S2 also expressed a preference for physical books, noting that reading with a paperback was more enjoyable than using a tablet. This made subsequent listening sessions feel easier and more natural. In the post-survey and guided interview, S2 commented that the audiobook's intonation "matched the characters well" and "complemented the book," enhancing their emotional connection with the story. S2 summarized their growing appreciation by stating, "I am likely to use audiobooks more in the future."

Overall, S2's motivation to read was consistently stronger during the RBL phase. They remarked, "I could understand the story better after reading; then listening helped me feel the characters' emotion and motivation." This suggests that reading supported comprehension, while listening enhanced emotional engagement. This pattern aligns with Eccles and Wigfield's (2002) expectancy-value theory, which proposes that motivation is shaped by perceived competence and the value placed on the task. S2's increased motivation during the RBL sequence may reflect both a greater sense of control and a clearer understanding of the material, which are important motivational drivers (Kartal & Simsek, 2017). Notably, S2's pre-survey responses indicated that reading in English was not a fun activity, which makes the increased motivation during RBL particularly significant as it suggests that the sequencing helped transform their engagement with reading.

The Case of Student 3 (S3)

Linguistic and reading background and experience before the study

S3 was a second-year university student majoring in Nursing who has studied English for over 10 years. Unlike S1 and S2, S3 did not express a particular preference for literary texts prior to the study and reported moderate confidence in both reading and listening skills. S3's prior experience with audiobooks was limited, and there was no strong habit of using them regularly.

Performance and participation during the study

S3 began the study following the Listening Before Reading (LBR) sequence for the first twelve chapters, then switched to Reading Before Listening (RBL) for the remaining chapters. S3 listened to audiobook chapters more than once during the LBR phase, demonstrating active engagement with the listening material despite initial comprehension challenges.

S3 commented, "Reading helped me understand the story more. I didn't catch everything when listening," indicating that reading was perceived as more effective for comprehension.

In terms of engagement, S3 noted, "Talking about why we liked the ending helped me form my own view more than just reading or listening alone," highlighting the

value of discussion in reinforcing comprehension and critical thinking beyond individual study.

In the group discussion, S3 reflected that hearing classmates explain their opinions “made some confusing parts clearer,” showing how peer discussion supported deeper understanding of the text.

Spelling accuracy showed moderate improvement during the RBL phase, with some lingering difficulties during the LBR phase, likely due to limited initial visual exposure to the text. Evaluating spelling performance for S3 during the first spelling assessment of the LBR phase proved more difficult due to several unanswered items, which affected the clarity of the results. Thus, reading first appeared to support stronger orthographic learning.

Time spent reading was fairly stable, averaging about 7–12 minutes per chapter in both phases, suggesting consistent participation throughout the study.

S3’s reading/listening logs indicated consistent effort: 2–3 readings per chapter (about 8–14 minutes), while audiobook listening became less frequent (1–2 times) after switching to RBL. This shift reflects growing confidence with the text through visual input.

Effects on motivation to read using audiobooks and following RBL and LBR

In the post-survey, S3 reported increased motivation to read after using the RBL sequence. S3 noted that “reading first helped [them] know what was happening,”

making the audiobook easier to follow. This sequencing appeared to increase enjoyment and reduce frustration, supporting a more sustainable interest in reading English material. Despite initial interest in audiobooks, S3 ultimately found reading more effective as the primary source of input.

S3's experience suggests that while listening can enrich emotional engagement, reading remains crucial for detailed understanding, especially for learners less familiar with audiobooks. This aligns with Eccles and Wigfield's (2002) motivation theory, where perceived competence and ease of processing influence sustained reading motivation.

Figure 3

Bar graph on quiz scores before and after each sequence

As Figure 3 shows, Student 1 gained +10 points in the RBL phase and +6 in the LBR phase; Student 2 gained +6 in LBR and +10 in RBL; Student 3 gained +13 in LBR and +1 in RBL.

Summary of Student Cases

While a sample of three cases cannot yield definitive conclusions, the patterns emerging from their performance and participation offer valuable insights into how Reading Before Listening (RBL) and Listening Before Reading (LBR) sequencing may influence EFL learners' outcomes.

During the RBL phases, all three students showed consistent gains in reading comprehension through the literal, inferential, and evaluative questions. Reading the

text first seems to have provided a visual scaffold, which was later reinforced by listening. As Figure 3 illustrates, each student's quiz score climbed during the RBL segments, reflecting improvements in recalling explicit details and forming critical judgments about the text.

This pattern underscores the role of visual text processing in driving comprehension and retention. As Brown (2011) suggests, reading strengthens recall by enabling learners to visually process and mentally rehearse textual details. The students' improved performance during RBL phases—particularly in literal and evaluative comprehension—supports this notion, illustrating how sustained visual input provides a firmer cognitive foundation that listening alone may not immediately establish.

These findings are consistent with Chang's (2011) research, which highlights the role of visual input in helping learners recognize and remember spelling patterns. They also support Paivio's Dual Coding Theory (1986), which proposes that combining visual and auditory inputs strengthens memory retention.

Spelling accuracy likewise benefited most from RBL. When students read before listening, their ability to correctly reproduce proper nouns and challenging vocabulary improved more sharply. These orthographic gains underscore the necessity of visual exposure for accurate spelling—supporting Kim's (2019, 2021) assertion that written input conveys precise letter sequences, Albeshier's (2018) findings on the limited orthographic effectiveness of audio-only exposure, Al-Jarf's (2005) conclusion that EFL learners rely heavily on visual word forms to internalize correct spelling patterns, and

Chang's (2011) observation that reading input provides learners with stable, repeatable exposure to language structures, including spelling conventions.

This pattern was particularly evident in Student 1. In the first half of the study (RBL), S1 frequently misspelled alien and human character names and made several persistent vocabulary errors. However, during the second half (LBR), spelling accuracy improved notably—especially in proper nouns and phonetically similar words (e.g., “tale” corrected to “tail,” and “gorila” corrected to “gorilla”). The combination of audio context followed by written reinforcement appeared to enhance orthographic precision over time (Chang, 2011).

Evaluating spelling performance for S2 and S3 during the LBR phase proved more difficult due to several unanswered items, which likely contributed to their lower scores during that phase (see Figure 3). However, in the RBL stage, spelling was more accurate, with only a few minor mistakes—likely attributable to typographical errors rather than true spelling deficiencies. This further reinforces the role of reading in supporting visual word recognition and correct spelling, particularly when learners are given time to process written input before hearing the target language (Al-Jarf, 2005; Albeshar, 2018).

In addition to quiz scores and survey responses, students' reading and listening logs offered nuanced insight into motivation and engagement patterns. Notably, S2 and S3, who reported greater enjoyment during the RBL phase, spent more time reading than listening, suggesting a preference for visual text processing. Both students consistently read each chapter 2–3 times, often spending 8–14 minutes per session.

Their listening behavior became more restrained in the latter half of the study, with S3, for instance, reducing audiobook playback to just 1–2 times per chapter after switching to RBL. This shift suggests that when reading came first, comprehension improved and reliance on audio diminished, as students drew more from their growing understanding of the story (Mutsaers, 2020).

In contrast, S1, who reported higher motivation during the LBR phase, demonstrated a different pattern. This student read and listened to each chapter only once, but used the audio input as a primary tool for initial comprehension and visualization. Listening appeared to support early memory recall, while later on, S1 relied on the audiobook to reinforce meaning after reading.

This behavior aligns with Saito et al. (2023), who highlight the motivational role of oral input in L2 learning, particularly in enhancing engagement through prosody, tone, and pacing. It also supports Dörnyei's (2005) L2 Motivational Self System and Deci and Ryan's (1985) Self-Determination Theory, which emphasize emotional investment, future language selves, and perceived competence. Each student appeared to gravitate toward the modality they felt most confident in—whether reading or listening—and invested time and cognitive effort accordingly. This supports Eccles and Wigfield's (2002) findings that learners devote greater effort to tasks they find both enjoyable and personally meaningful.

Finally, motivation data suggest that RBL sequencing in particular bolstered learners' confidence and engagement, consistent with Expectancy-Value Theory (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002) and the L2 Motivational Self System (Dörnyei, 2005). When

text preceded audio, participants reported increased feelings of competence and preparedness, which contributed to stronger task value, self-efficacy, and longer-term motivation.

Together, these findings support the conceptual framework outlined in Chapter 2, which proposed that initial visual engagement anchors orthographic representations—thereby reducing cognitive load during subsequent listening—and that alternating modalities harness both Paivio’s (1986) dual channels and Mayer’s (2005) segmenting principle to optimize comprehension and retention.

In contrast, the LBR phases yielded smaller spelling improvements due to unanswered questions during chapters 1-12 and slightly lower literal comprehension gains, echoing Dich and Pedersen’s (2013) finding that audio-only input can lead to phonetic decoding errors. Nonetheless, LBR enriched inferential understanding—students often experienced strong jumps in inferential scores after reading, supporting Mayer’s Segmenting Principle (2005)—and heightened emotional engagement. Student 1 noted, “After listening first, I felt I could imagine more without focusing on reading,” reflecting the affective benefits identified by Kartal and Simsek (2017). Audio preview scaffolds comprehension, as Rogowsky, Calhoun, and Tallal (2016) argue, by priming mental models that reading then elaborates.

Evaluative comprehension gains in both sequences benefited from post-quiz discussions where students verbalized opinions which is supported by Sweller’s Cognitive Load Theory (1988), which proposes that active discussion frees working memory for higher-order thinking. On the other hand, RBL appears particularly effective

for enhancing literal and inferential comprehension, spelling accuracy, and learner confidence, whereas LBR can deepen inferential understanding and emotional engagement. This supports Swallow's (2016) view that students must grasp meaning with the same clarity as they decode written words, highlighting the value of sequencing that promotes both surface and deeper processing. Purposefully combining modalities—reading to anchor orthographic forms and listening to animate text—may therefore optimize comprehension, orthographic learning, and learner motivation.

Taken together, these patterns underscore the importance of purposeful audiobook sequencing—RBL to reinforce spelling and literal comprehension, and LBR to support inferencing and motivation. This approach supports Dual Coding Theory (Paivio, 1986) and contemporary motivational frameworks, and illuminates how modality order shapes EFL learning outcomes, setting the stage for broader pedagogical implications and theoretical contributions in the next chapter.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, & RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Key Findings

This study explored the potential effects of two audiobook sequencing strategies—Reading Before Listening (RBL) and Listening Before Reading (LBR)—on university EFL students' reading comprehension, spelling accuracy, and motivation. While not intended to establish causality, the study aimed to identify patterns of influence and student responses to each sequence. Across the three students, clear trends emerged that align with the research questions and theoretical framework.

Reading Comprehension

All three participants demonstrated improvement in literal, inferential, and evaluative comprehension scores after switching sequences. For instance, Student 1 (S1), who began with Reading Before Listening (RBL) and then switched to Listening Before Reading (LBR), showed a notable increase in inferential comprehension scores in the second half of the study. This outcome reflects Chang (2011), who reported deeper understanding following integrated input. These findings also support Kim (2019), who emphasized the benefits of dual modalities, and align with Baron (2021) and Brown (2011), who stressed that reading tends to yield higher long-term retention.

Students 2 and 3, who transitioned from LBR to RBL, engaged in repeated readings and multiple listening sessions, showing steady growth in comprehension. These

patterns are consistent with Kim (2021), who argued that repeated exposure across modalities enhances comprehension.

Spelling Accuracy

Although the LBR sequence introduced new vocabulary through auditory input, it was the RBL sequence that led to stronger orthographic gains over time. After switching to RBL, Students 2 and 3 achieved near-perfect spelling of proper nouns and corrected earlier vocabulary errors. This trend supports Albeshier (2018), who highlighted the role of visual exposure in spelling acquisition, and aligns with Saito et al. (2023), who emphasized the reinforcement effect of phonological input following visual encoding.

Motivation and Engagement

Although no formal motivation scale was used, qualitative data—including reading logs, survey responses, and interview transcripts—revealed increased intrinsic motivation during both sequencing phases. For example, S1 shared, “Listening helped me visualize the scenes more clearly,” while S2 noted, “Reading was easier for me to follow, whereas the audiobook was fast.” Such comments reflect a sense of autonomy and perceived competence, which are central tenets of Deci and Ryan’s (1985) Self-Determination Theory.

The findings also resonate with Kartal & Simsek (2017), who found that audiobooks promote sustained voluntary reading, and Eccles & Wigfield’s (2002) expectancy-value theory, which posits that motivation is influenced by perceived task value and self-efficacy.

To synthesize the patterns across comprehension, spelling, and motivation, the following flow chart illustrates the primary effects of each sequencing strategy and the observed benefits after switching methods.

Figure 4

Sequencing Effects on EFL Learners' Reading Comprehension, Spelling Accuracy, and Motivation

As shown in Figure 4, the RBL sequence primarily supported spelling accuracy and surface-level comprehension, whereas the LBR sequence fostered deeper inferential skills and visualization. The sequencing switch created opportunities for students to gain from both approaches, leading to a more holistic learning outcome. This supports the use of flexible, blended sequencing models in EFL reading programs to enhance language acquisition across multiple dimensions.

Sequencing Effects and Theoretical Alignment:

This research revealed that sequencing effects map neatly onto the theoretical frameworks:

- **Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988):** Alternating between reading and listening helped distribute cognitive demands across visual and auditory modalities. For example, Student 1's switch from RBL to LBR seemed to reduce the mental burden of decoding text alone, allowing more cognitive capacity for inferential comprehension. Similarly, Students 2 and 3 benefited from RBL in the second half, as visual input reduced ambiguity in word recognition previously introduced during listening
- **Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning (Mayer, 2005):** Sequencing verbal (audio) and visual (text) inputs—rather than presenting them simultaneously—prevented cognitive redundancy and allowed for more efficient integration of information. Student 3, for example, demonstrated stronger evaluative comprehension after the LBR-to-RBL switch, likely because prior listening

created a mental scaffold that was reinforced by subsequent reading, supporting Mayer's principle of modality and temporal contiguity.

- **Dual Coding Theory (Paivio, 1986):** The combined use of auditory and visual channels supported dual encoding of information, which in turn strengthened memory retrieval. This was evident in the improved spelling accuracy of Students 2 and 3 after switching to RBL. Having first heard unfamiliar proper nouns in context (LBR), they were later able to encode those words visually and recall them more accurately, illustrating Paivio's assertion that multimodal representation enhances recall.
- **Transfer Stage (Fries, 1945):** Sequencing effects also reflect Fries' theory of transfer between modalities. Listening-first exposure (LBR) helped prime recognition when students encountered the same content in print, while reading-first exposure (RBL) improved auditory parsing later. These patterns were most visible after the midpoint switch, when all three students showed measurable improvements across comprehension levels and spelling.

Conclusion

This study confirms that sequencing **does** matter, as the research questions and assumptions were addressed meaningfully:

What is the effect of RBL on selected university EFL students':

a. reading comprehension?

- b. spelling?
- c. intrinsic motivation to read?

What is the effect of LBR on selected university EFL students’:

- a. reading comprehension?
- b. spelling?
- c. intrinsic motivation to read?

Confirmation of Assumptions

The study's initial assumptions centered on how audiobook sequencing might affect comprehension, spelling accuracy, and, to a lesser extent, motivation. Specifically, it was assumed that Listening Before Reading (LBR) would enhance comprehension and retention by providing early auditory exposure to the target language. This assumption was partially confirmed: Student 1, who switched from Reading Before Listening (RBL) to LBR midway, showed improved inferential comprehension, supporting the idea that listening can prime understanding when paired with reading. However, the clearest comprehension gains were observed after switching sequences, suggesting that a combination of modalities—rather than the initial sequence alone—was most effective.

The second assumption was that Reading Before Listening (RBL) would lead to stronger initial spelling accuracy due to early visual exposure to the orthographic forms of words. This assumption was strongly supported. Students who switched to RBL showed immediate improvements in their spelling of proper nouns and vocabulary that

had previously been spelled inconsistently. Additionally, the anticipated reinforcement effect from switching to LBR was observed in Student 1, suggesting that auditory review after visual encoding may also contribute positively to orthographic development.

Regarding motivation, the study made no fixed assumptions. Instead, it aimed to explore how sequencing might have an effect on students' intrinsic motivation. The results revealed that both sequencing methods contributed to increased engagement and perceived autonomy, though in different ways. While LBR enhanced students' ability to visualize content and build narrative anticipation, RBL supported confidence by clarifying vocabulary and structure early. These findings suggest that motivation is not strictly dependent on sequence but may be shaped by students' individual preferences and the perceived benefits of each modality.

Key findings include:

- **LBR** best supports inferential comprehension and initial motivation, especially for learners who struggle with printed text alone.
- **RBL** is particularly effective for reinforcing orthographic knowledge and literal recall when followed by audio.
- Switching sequencing methods mid-study contributed to growth in both skills, supporting a blended or alternating approach to modality use.
- A **blended or alternating approach**, tailored to individual learning preferences, yields the most balanced outcomes.

Understanding learner profiles—such as visual vs. auditory preference—moderate these effects, underscoring the need for learner-centered sequencing.

Recommendations

For EFL Instructors:

Incorporate both RBL and LBR in lesson plans. Use RBL to target spelling and vocabulary recall, and use LBR to scaffold comprehension tasks, thereby leveraging the strengths of both modalities.

For Curriculum Designers:

Develop modules that alternate reading and listening sequencing phases, accompanied by guided reflection questions to stimulate evaluative thinking and track engagement.

For Researchers:

- Expand the sample size and participant diversity to test generalizability across different demographics and proficiency levels.
- Explore sequencing with various text genres such as nonfiction or academic articles.
- Integrate formal motivation instruments for a more solid quantitative validation.

Limitations

Several factors constrain the generalizability and scope of this study:

- **Small, non-random sample.** With only three participants—and one withdrawal—findings reflect the experiences of highly motivated students and may not apply to the broader EFL population.
- **Group imbalance.** The 2-vs-1 grouping after the dropout limits balanced comparisons and may introduce bias.
- **Manual data analysis.** Scores and thematic coding were conducted manually, which, while appropriate for a small case study (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Yin, 2018), may be less replicable than automated methods.
- **Lack of formal motivation measures.** Motivation was inferred from surveys, logs, and interviews rather than assessed with standardized instruments, limiting precision.
- **Single text genre.** Using only *Animorphs* constrains the understanding of sequencing effects across different genres or academic texts.
- **Short duration.** The short spanned a short period (about one month), which may not capture long-term retention or sustained motivation patterns.

Despite its limitations, this study is one of the first—if not the first—to explicitly investigate the sequencing of Reading Before Listening (RBL) and Listening Before Reading (LBR) in EFL audiobook use. The findings offer valuable insights into how sequencing affects comprehension, spelling accuracy, and motivation, providing a

meaningful contribution to both research and pedagogy in multimodal language learning.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: ORIGINAL AND REVISED PRE-SURVEY

Original Pre-Survey

Reading & Audiobook

This survey is designed to understand your experiences with books and audiobooks. Names and personal information will be confidential and in no way be revealed without signed consent.

1. What year are you in university?
 1. First year
 - b. second year
 - c. third year
 - d. Fourth year
 - e. other
2. What is your major? _____
3. What is your gender?
 1. Male
 - b. Female
 - c. other
4. I have studied English for_____.
 1. Less than a year
 - b. 1-2 years
 - c. 3-5 years
 - d. 6-10 years
 - e. more than 10 years

Reading and Listening Experience

The next set of questions are going to ask you about your reading experiences and audiobook experiences in English and/or Korean. Please answer truthfully and as best as possible.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
My English is good.					
My English listening is good.					
My English reading is good.					
I enjoy reading novels.					

I enjoy reading novels in Korean.					
I enjoy reading novels in English.					
I can read novels in English.					
I read for fun.					
I read for school.					
Reading is important to me.					
Reading English texts is an easy task.					

Reading English texts is a difficult task.					
I have listened to audiobooks in Korean.					
I have listened to audiobooks in English.					
Listening to English is easy.					
Listening to English is difficult.					
Audio material helps me to understand more.					

Visual materials helps me to understand more.					
Listening helps me to remember more.					
Reading helps me to remember more.					
When I was young, my parents read to me a lot					
I have access to many types of reading materials.					
I like to read the media when commuting on public					

transportation .					
I like to listen to the media when commuting on public transportation .					
I read for at least 30 minutes a day.					
I listen to media at least 30 minutes a day.					

Revised Pre Survey

Reading & Audiobook

This survey is to designed to understand your experiences with books and audiobooks. Names and personal information will be confidential and in no way be revealed without signed consent.

1. What year are you in university?

- a. First year b. second year c. third year d. Fourth year e.
other

2. What is your major? _____

3. What is your gender?

- a. Male b. Female c. other

4. I have studied English for_____.

- a. Less than a year b. 1-2 years c. 3-5 years d. 6-10 years e. more than
10 years

Reading and Listening Experience

The next set of questions are going to ask you about your reading experiences and audiobook experiences in English and/or Korean. Please answer truthfully and as best as possible.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
My English listening is good.					
My English reading is good.					
I want to improve my English listening skills.					
I want to improve my English reading skills.					
I enjoy reading materials in English.					
I can read novels in English.					

I enjoy reading novels in English.					
I read for fun.					
I read for school.					
Reading is important to me.					
Reading English texts is an easy task.					
I find it easy to understand the main ideas in English texts.					
I pay attention to spelling when I read English texts.					

I feel confident spelling most English words correctly.					
I have listened to audiobooks in English.					
Listening to English is easy.					
Listening to audio materials helps me understand better.					
Visual materials helps me to understand more.					
Listening helps me to remember more.					

Reading helps me to remember more.					
I feel more motivated to learn English when I can do both reading and listening activities					
My parents read to me when I was a child.					
I have access to many types of reading materials.					
I have access to many types of audio materials.					
I like to read when commuting.					

I like to listen when commuting.					
I read for at least 30 minutes a day.					
I listen to media at least 30 minutes a day.					

APPENDIX B: ORIGINAL AND REVISED POST SURVEY¹

Original Post Survey

Part I. Students' involvement with the audiobook and book during the study

1. Please mark the option that corresponds to your answer.

() I listened to the audio recording first, and I read the story later. Was it beneficial? Why or why not?

() I read the story first, and I listened to the audio recording later. Was it beneficial? Why or why not?

2. **() I read the story once.**

() I read the story more than once. Why?

¹ This questionnaire was designed in another study. (Turker, 2010) Since it was already created by the researcher, tested, and validated, thus it was chosen to be the post survey of this research. The questions are not verbatim, nor are they copyrighted. The format of the questions was kept similar.

3. () I listened to the audio recording once.

() I listened to the audio recording more than once. Why?

Part II. Students' attitudes towards audiobooks

1. Did you like to read the book before() after() to the audio recording?

Please explain. yes () no ()

2. Did listening to the audio before() after ()reading the book maake it easier for you to understand the story? Please explain. yes () no ()

3. Did the intonation of the speaker make it easier for you to understand the audiobook? Please explain. yes () no ()

5. Do you prefer reading audio books to reading other printed materials? Please explain. yes () no ()

6. Do you think you will listen to audiobooks more to help with your English? Please explain. Yes () no ()

Thank you for your contribution!

Revised Post Survey

Part I: Students' Engagement with the Audiobook and Book

1. How did you prefer to engage with the materials?
 - I listened to the audiobook first, then read the story.
 - I read the story first, then listened to the audiobook.
 - *Was this approach beneficial? Why or why not?*
2. How many times did you read the story?
 - Once
 - More than once
 - *If more than once, why?*
3. How many times did you listen to the audiobook?
 - Once
 - More than once
 - *If more than once, why?*

Part II: Students' Attitudes Toward Audiobooks

4. Reading the book before listening to the audiobook made it easier to understand the story.
 - Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 - *Why or why not?*
5. Listening to the audiobook before reading made it easier to understand the story.
 - Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
 - *Why or why not?*

6. The narrator's intonation helped me understand the audiobook.
- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
- *Why or why not?*
7. I prefer audiobooks over printed materials.
- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
- *Why or why not?*
8. After this study, I am more likely to use audiobooks to improve my English.
- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
- *Why or why not?*
9. Listening to an audiobook made me more engaged with the story compared to reading alone.
- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
- *Why or why not?*
10. After this study, I am more interested in reading English books for pleasure.
- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
- *Why or why not?*
11. Listening to the audiobook helped me recognize and remember the spelling of new words.
- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree
- *Which words were the most difficult to remember?*
12. I felt confident answering comprehension questions after using both the book and audiobook.
- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

- *What helped you the most in understanding the story?*

Thank you for your contribution!

APPENDIX C: CONSENT FORM

University of the Philippines Open University INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH

ETHICS COMMITTEE

Dear students/participants,

This study has been designed to collect data for a master's thesis conducted for the MALLE Program at the University of the Philippines Open University. Your participation will contribute to exploring the effectiveness of audiobooks and reading sequencing in enhancing the reading comprehension and vocabulary retention of university EFL students and understanding attitudes toward using audiobooks.

Your responses will be kept confidential, and your identity will not be disclosed in any reports or presentations derived from this study. Participation in this study is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw at any time without consequences. However, withdrawing will give the research incomplete data, and your participation throughout the study will give the clearest results.

If you agree to participate in this study, please sign this form. Should you have any questions or need further information, please contact [Mason Williams] at [masonwilliams@kornu.ac.kr].

Mandatory

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Print Name of Participant: _____

Signature of Participant: _____

University of the Philippines Open University INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH
ETHICS COMMITTEE

Dear students/participants,

This study has been designed to collect data for a master's thesis conducted for the MALLE Program at the University of the Philippines Open University. Your participation will contribute to exploring the effectiveness of audiobooks and reading sequencing in enhancing the reading comprehension and vocabulary retention of university EFL students and understanding attitudes toward using audiobooks.

Your responses will be kept confidential, and your identity will not be disclosed in any reports or presentations derived from this study. Participation in this study is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw at any time without consequences. However, withdrawing will give the research incomplete data, and your participation throughout the study will give the clearest results.

If you agree to participate in this study, please sign this form. Should you have any questions or need further information, please contact [Mason Williams] at [masonwilliams@kornu.ac.kr].

Mandatory

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Print Name of Participant: _____ Ji Yoon _____

Signature of Participant: _____

University of the Philippines Open University INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH
ETHICS COMMITTEE

Dear students/participants,

This study has been designed to collect data for a master's thesis conducted for the MALLE Program at the University of the Philippines Open University. Your participation will contribute to exploring the effectiveness of audiobooks and reading sequencing in enhancing the reading comprehension and vocabulary retention of university EFL students and understanding attitudes toward using audiobooks.

Your responses will be kept confidential, and your identity will not be disclosed in any reports or presentations derived from this study. Participation in this study is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw at any time without consequences. However, withdrawing will give the research incomplete data, and your participation throughout the study will give the clearest results.

If you agree to participate in this study, please sign this form. Should you have any questions or need further information, please contact [Mason Williams] at [masonwilliams@kornu.ac.kr].

Mandatory

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Print Name of Participant: _____ Suhyun Kim _____

Signature of Participant: _____

University of the Philippines Open University INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH
ETHICS COMMITTEE

Dear students/participants,

This study has been designed to collect data for a master's thesis conducted for the MALLE Program at the University of the Philippines Open University. Your participation will contribute to exploring the effectiveness of audiobooks and reading sequencing in enhancing the reading comprehension and vocabulary retention of university EFL students and understanding attitudes toward using audiobooks.

Your responses will be kept confidential, and your identity will not be disclosed in any reports or presentations derived from this study. Participation in this study is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw at any time without consequences. However, withdrawing will give the research incomplete data, and your participation throughout the study will give the clearest results.

If you agree to participate in this study, please sign this form. Should you have any questions or need further information, please contact [Mason Williams] at [masonwilliams@kornu.ac.kr].

Mandatory

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Print Name of Participant: Kyu Rhi Ahn

Signature of Participant: Kyu Rhi Ahn

APPENDIX D: ORIGINAL AND REVISED CHAPTERS 1-12 AND 13-27

QUIZZES

Original Quiz

Chapters 1-12

1. What are the names of the five kids?

Jake, Marco, Cassie, Rachel, Tobias

2. Which person is telling the story?

Jake

3. What does the main character and his friend like to do?

play video games

4. What is the main character's brother's name?

Tom

5. What does the brother like to do?

play basketball

6. What is the first alien race called?

Andalite

7. How big was the space ship?

as big as a bus

8. What shape was the space ship?

like an egg

9. How does the alien communicate?

By thinking

10. What color is the andalite?

blue

11. How many eyes does the alien have?

4

12. What kind of tail does the alien have?

Scorpion

13. Is he the first alien?

No

14. What is the name of the other aliens that the andalite doesn't like?

Yeerks

15. Are these aliens friendly?

No

16. What part of the body do Yeerks enter?

ear

17. Who are Controllers?

hosts

18. What does Jake get off the ship?

A blue box

19. What power does the Andalite want to give the kids?

morph

20. What do the kids have to copy to get the power?

DNA

21. What are the Yeerk's ships called?

Bug Fighter

22.. What is the maximum time the kids can stay in animal form?

2 hours

23. What happens if they stay over the maximum time?

They stay as that animal.

24. What is a Yeerk leader called?

visser

25. What is the good Andalite's name?

Prince Elfangor

26. What alien host Visser Three?

andalite

27. What did Jake pick up?

a pipe

28. Who led the hork-bajirs away from their friends?

Jake and Rachel

29. Which friend came to Jake's house?

Tobias

30. What was the first animal that Tobias turned into?

a cat

31. What does Tobias want Jake to do when he is a cat?

play

32. Whose brain does Tobias have when he is morphed?

Both his brain and the animal's brain

33. What does Tobias not have when he turns back into human?

clothes

34. What does Tobias think Jake is?

a leader

35. Who is Homer?

a dog

36. How did Jake become Homer?

He concentrated on becoming him.

37. What was the first body part that changed?

Hands

38. How did Jake first feel when he was a dog?

happy

39. Who knocked on Jake's door?

Tom

40. Where did the teenagers meet later?

at a farm

41. What club did Tom join?

The Sharing

42. What is The Gardens?

a zoo

43. What animal did Cassie turn into?

a horse

44. Who came to Cassie's farm?

a police officer

45. What kind of clothing can they morph into?

skin tight clothing

46. How do they decide if they will fight the yeerks?

by voting

47. What kind of bird did Tobias morph into?

a red-tail hawk

48. What did Tobias fly on?

Thermals

49. What do Yeerks need every three days?

Kadrona Rays

Chapters 13-27

1. What does Tobias suggest that The Sharing is?

An organization for Controllers

2. Where was the sharing meeting?

the beach

3. What animal does Jake morph into at the sharing meeting?

a dog

4. Which person from Jake's school was at the Sharing meeting?

assistant principal

5. What kind of lizard did Jake morph into?

anole lizard

6. Where did he morph?

in his locker

7. What did he eat when he was a lizard?

a spider

8. What body part did the shoe step on?

his tail

9. Where did Jake follow Mr. Chapman?

the janitor's closet

10. What did Jake hear in that room?

screams

11. What do the kids decide to do with the Yeerks?

fight them

12. Who suggests the name Animorphs?

Marco

13. What kind of animal is Big Jim?

A gorilla

14. Who gets Big Jim's DNA?

Marco

15. What animal exhibit did Jake and Marco run into?

A tiger

16. Who touches the animal in the exhibit?

Jake

17. What food does Jake's mom tell him to eat?

broccoli

18. Who has Cassie?

Controllers

19. How do the kids go into the Janitor's office?

they pretend to be Controllers

20. Where are the people without Yeerks placed?

in a cage

21. What are Collaborators?

voluntary hosts

22. What animal do you think Rachel turns into?

an elephant

23. What animal did Jake turn into?

a tiger

24. What does Marco tell everyone to call him?

King Kong

25. What body part did Tobias attack on the Hork-Bajir?

their eyes

26. Who does Visser Three think the kids are?

andalites

27. What did Visser Three shoot at the kids?

fireballs

28. Who do the Animorphs rescue?

a woman

29. How long does Tobias stay as a hawk?

for more than two hours

30. Who does Tobias say will come?

more Andalites

31. What will the Animorphs do in the meantime?

Fight

Revised Quiz

Animorphs Reading Comprehension Quiz (Chapters 1-12)

Instructions:

- Answer each question to the best of your ability.
- This quiz consists of 45 questions.
- You have 90 minutes to complete it.
- Spell check is disabled, so do your best with spelling.
- If unsure about a question, move on and return later.
- The instructor will assist as needed.

Literal-Level Comprehension (Basic Recall) 28 Questions

1. What are the names of the five kids?

Answer: Jake, Marco, Cassie, Rachel, Tobias

2. Who is the narrator of the story?

Answer: Jake

3. What do Jake and Marco like to do for fun?

Answer: Play video games

4. What is Jake's brother's name?

Answer: Tom

5. What is the name of the first alien race introduced?

Answer: Andalite

6. What shape is the Andalite spaceship?

Answer: Like an egg

7. How does the Andalite communicate?

Answer: By thinking (telepathy)

8. How many eyes does an Andalite have?

Answer: Four

9. What is the Andalite's name?

Answer: Prince Elfangor

10. What special ability does the Andalite give to the kids?

Answer: Morphing

11. How do the kids acquire the ability to morph?

Answer: By touching an animal and absorbing its DNA

12. What is the maximum time the kids can stay in animal form?

Answer: Two hours

13. What happens if they stay past the time limit?

Answer: They remain trapped as that animal permanently.

14. What is the name of the alien species that takes over human bodies?

Answer: Yeerks

15. Where do the Yeerks enter a person's body?

Answer: Through the ear

16. What is the title given to a Yeerk leader?

Answer: Visser

17. What is the name of the organization Tom is involved in?

Answer: The Sharing

18. What kind of animal does Tobias morph into first?

Answer: A cat

19. What do Yeerks need to survive every three days?

Answer: Kandrona Rays

20. Where do the kids meet to discuss their plans?

Answer: At a farm

21. How do the Yeerks control their human hosts?

Answer: By entering their brains

22. What happens to a host when a Yeerk leaves their body?

Answer: They regain control of themselves.

23. What do the Yeerks use to feed their species?

Answer: Kandrona Rays

24. What does the Andalite warn the kids about before he dies?

Answer: The Yeerks are taking over Earth.

25. What happens when the kids first attempt to morph?

Answer: They struggle to control the animal instincts.

26. Why does Tobias have trouble morphing back?

Answer: He doesn't have on any clothes.

27. What do the kids discover about the Yeerk Pool?

Answer: It's where Yeerks return to feed.

28. Who is Visser Three, and why is he important?

Answer: He is the only Andalite-Controller and the main villain.

Inferential-Level Comprehension (Reading Between the Lines) 10 Questions

29. Why do you think the Andalite chooses to give the morphing ability to the kids instead of fighting the Yeerks himself?

Answer: He is injured and dying, so he needs someone to continue the fight.

30. Why is Tom so eager to recruit Jake into The Sharing?

Answer: Tom is a Controller and wants to make Jake one, too.

31. How do the Andalites and Yeerks differ in their goals?

Answer: Andalites want to protect free will; Yeerks want to control others.

32. What clues suggest that Jake is becoming the leader of the group?

Answer: The others look to him for decisions and guidance.

33. Why does Tobias enjoy being a hawk more than the others enjoy their morphs?

Answer: He feels free and powerful as a hawk.

34. Why does Visser Three seem more dangerous than other Controllers?

Answer: He is the only Yeerk in an Andalite body, giving him morphing powers.

35. Why might the kids be hesitant to trust anyone outside their group?

Answer: Anyone could be a Controller.

36. What are some risks of using their morphing ability in public?

Answer: They could be discovered by the Yeerks.

37. Why is the time limit for morphing important to the story?

Answer: It adds tension and forces them to act quickly.

38. What could happen if the Yeerks discovered that the kids had the morphing power?

Answer: The Yeerks would hunt them down.

Evaluative-Level Comprehension (Critical Thinking & Reflection)- 7 Questions

39. Do you think the Andalite made the right decision by giving the morphing power to the kids? Why or why not?

Answer: Open-ended

40. If you were in Jake's position, would you trust the Andalite? Why?

Answer: Open-ended

41. How does the theme of **power and control** play a role in the story?

Answer: Open-ended; can discuss Yeerks vs. Andalites, Controllers, free will

42. Do you think the kids should try to stop the Yeerks or just stay out of it? Explain.

Answer: Open-ended

43. What ethical issues do you see with the idea of morphing into another living being?

Answer: Open-ended; can discuss identity, animal rights, etc.

44. If you had the ability to morph, what animal would you choose and why?

Answer: Open-ended

45. What lessons can be learned from the kids' choices in the story?

Answer: Open-ended; can discuss teamwork, responsibility, courage

Animorphs Quiz: Chapters 13-27

Instructions:

- This quiz consists of 45 questions divided into literal, inferential, and evaluative sections.
- You have **90 minutes** to complete the quiz.
- The quiz is administered via **Google Forms**, with spell check disabled.
- Short-answer questions may require more than one word.
- If you are unsure about a spelling, do your best and move on.
- Your instructor will assist you as needed.

Literal Questions

1. What does Tobias suggest that The Sharing is?

Answer: An organization for Controllers

2. Where was the Sharing meeting?

Answer: The beach

3. What animal does Jake morph into at the Sharing meeting?
Answer: A dog
4. Which person from Jake's school was at the Sharing meeting?
Answer: Assistant principal
5. What kind of lizard did Jake morph into?
Answer: Anole lizard
6. Where did he morph?
Answer: In his locker
7. What did he eat when he was a lizard?
Answer: A spider
8. What body part did the shoe step on?
Answer: His tail
9. Where did Jake follow Mr. Chapman?
Answer: The janitor's closet
10. What did Jake hear in that room?
Answer: Screams
11. What do the kids decide to do with the Yeerks?
Answer: Fight them
12. Who suggests the name Animorphs?
Answer: Marco
13. What kind of animal is Big Jim?
Answer: A gorilla
14. Who gets Big Jim's DNA?
Answer: Marco
15. What animal exhibit did Jake and Marco run into?
Answer: A tiger
16. Who touches the animal in the exhibit?
Answer: Jake
17. What food does Jake's mom tell him to eat?

Answer: Broccoli

18. Who has Cassie?

Answer: Controllers

19. How do the kids go into the Janitor's office?

Answer: They pretend to be Controllers

20. Where are the people without Yeerks placed?

Answer: In a cage

21. What are Collaborators?

Answer: Voluntary hosts

22. What animal do you think Rachel turns into?

Answer: An elephant

23. What animal did Jake turn into?

Answer: A tiger

24. What does Marco tell everyone to call him?

Answer: King Kong

25. What body part did Tobias attack on the Hork-Bajir?

Answer: Their eyes

26. Who does Visser Three think the kids are?

Answer: Andalites

27. What did Visser Three shoot at the kids?

Answer: Fireballs

28. Who do the Animorphs rescue?

Answer: A woman

Inferential

Questions

29. How do the Animorphs feel about fighting the Yeerks?

Answer: Nervous but determined

30. Why does Marco suggest the name "Animorphs"?

Answer: It describes their ability to morph into animals

31. Why is Jake's ability to morph into a tiger significant?

Answer: It gives him power and confidence

32. Why do the Animorphs go to The Sharing meeting?

Answer: To investigate its connection to the Yeerks

33. What does Jake eating a spider as a lizard suggest?

Answer: He is losing control to the animal instincts

34. Why do they pretend to be Controllers to enter the Janitor's office?

Answer: To avoid suspicion and gain information

35. Why do voluntary hosts (Collaborators) exist?

Answer: They believe working with the Yeerks benefits them

36. How does Tobias staying in hawk form impact him?

Answer: He loses his human identity but gains freedom

37. What does Visser Three shooting fireballs tell us about him?

Answer: He is powerful and ruthless

38. Why does Tobias believe more Andalites will come?

Answer: He has hope that they are not alone in this fight

Evaluative Questions

39. Do you think Jake is a good leader? Why or why not?

Answer: Open-ended

40. What would you do if you were offered the ability to morph?

Answer: Open-ended

41. How do the Animorphs' choices compare to real-world resistance movements?

Answer: Open-ended

42. Do you think Marco's humor helps or hurts the team? Why?

Answer: Open-ended

43. What ethical dilemmas do the Animorphs face in their fight?

Answer: Open-ended

44. How do you feel about Tobias' decision to stay as a hawk?

Answer: Open-ended

45. If you could change one thing about how the Animorphs operate, what would it be?

Answer: Open-ended

APPENDIX E: ORIGINAL AND REVISED READING/LISTENING LOG

Original Log

Reading/listening LOG

Chapter	How many times did you read the chapter?	Timed Reading	How many times did you listen to the chapter? (# of times paused)	Timed Listening (speed)
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				
6				
7				
8				

9				
10				
11				
12				
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				
20				

21				
22				
23				
24				
25				
26				
27				

Revised Log

Instructions for Completing the Log

1. Track Your Reading and Listening

- Record how many times you read each chapter.
- Record how many times you listened to the audiobook and how often you paused.
- Note the speed at which you listened.

2. Reflect on Your Experience

- Answer the reflection questions after each session.

- Keep responses concise but meaningful.

3. Be Consistent

- Complete the log after each session to ensure accurate reflection.
- RBL and LBR groups should follow the same log structure.

Reading/listening LOG

Chapter	Times Read	Timed Reading	Times Listen ed	Pauses	Listening (speed)	Most challenging part?	How did you understand and the main idea?	Difficult words & spelling strategies?	Most interesting part? Why?
1									
2									
3									
4									
5									
6									

7									
8									
9									
10									
11									
12									
13									
14									
15									
16									
17									
18									

19									
20									
21									
22									
23									
24									
25									
26									
27									

APPENDIX F: PRE-SURVEY RESULTS

A. Participant Information

Student #	Year	Major
1	3rd	Counseling Psychology
2	2nd	Counseling Psychology
3	2nd	Nursing

B. English Language Experience

Student #	Years Studied English
1	More than 10 years

2	More than 10 years
3	More than 10 years

C. Self-Evaluation of English Listening and Reading Skills

- *Rating scale: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Neutral (3), Disagree (2), Strongly Disagree (1)*

Question	Student 1	Student 2	Student 3
Listening: My English listening is good.	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)
Reading: My English reading is good.	Neutral (3)	Neutral (3)	Neutral (3)
I want to improve my English listening skills.	Strongly Agree (5)	Strongly Agree (5)	Strongly Agree (5)

I want to improve my English reading skills.	Strongly Agree (5)	Strongly Agree (5)	Strongly Agree (5)
I enjoy reading novels.	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)
I enjoy reading novels in English.	Strongly Agree (5)	Disagree (2)	Disagree (2)
I can read novels in English.	Strongly Agree (5)	Neutral (3)	Neutral (3)
I read for fun.	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Agree (4)
I read for school.	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Agree (4)
Reading is important to me.	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Agree (4)

Reading English texts is easy.	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)
I find it easy to understand the main ideas in English texts.	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Neutral (3)
I pay attention to spelling when I read English texts.	Agree (4)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)
I feel confident spelling most English words correctly.	Disagree (2)	Strongly Agree (5)	Neutral (3)

D. Self-Evaluation of English Listening Materials

Question	Student 1	Student 2	Student 3
I have listened to audiobooks in English.	Strongly Agree (5)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)

Listening to English is easy.	Strongly Agree (5)	Disagree (2)	Agree (4)
Audio materials help me understand more.	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)
Visual materials help me understand more.	Neutral (3)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)
Listening helps me remember more.	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Agree (4)
Reading helps me remember more.	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)
I feel more motivated to learn English when I can do both reading and listening activities.	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Agree (4)

E. Reading and Listening Habits

Question	Student 1	Student 2	Student 3
When I was young, my parents read to me a lot.	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)
I have access to many types of reading materials.	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Neutral (3)
I like to read media when commuting.	Strongly Agree (5)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Neutral (3)
I like to listen to the media when commuting.	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)
I read for at least 30 minutes a day.	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Neutral (3)
I listen to the media at least 30 minutes a day.	Agree (4)	Agree (4)	Agree (4)

APPENDIX G: SUMMARY OF POST SURVEY LIKERT-STYLE RESPONSES

(Questions 4a–12a)

(Likert scale: Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly Agree)

Item	Statement	Student 1	Student 2	Student 3
4a	Reading before listening made it easier to understand the story.	Disagree	Neutral	Strongly Agree
5a	Listening before reading made it easier to understand the story.	Strongly Agree	Neutral	Disagree
6a	The narrator's intonation helped me understand the audiobook.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Neutral
7a	I prefer audiobooks over printed materials.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree

8a	After this study, I'm more likely to use audiobooks to improve my English.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
9a	Listening to an audiobook made me more engaged with the story than reading alone.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
10a	I'm more interested in reading English books for pleasure after this study.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree
11a	Listening to the audiobook helped me recognize and remember the spelling of new words.	Neutral	Neutral	Disagree
12a	I felt confident answering comprehension questions after using both the book and audiobook.	Neutral	Disagree	Agree

APPENDIX H: STUDENT READING LOGS (Students 1-3)

Student 1 Reading/listening LOG

Chapter	Time s Read	Timed Readin g	Times Listene d	Pause s	Listenin g (speed)	Most challengin g part?	How did you underst and the main idea?	Difficult words & spelling strategi es?	Most interest ing part? Why?
1	1	10m	1	3(there was a person in my room)	1.0	X	Intrusting	X	Flying saucer / It's sounds funny
2	1	8m	1	0	1.0	X		Writing down words and spell it repeatin gly	<<THE Y HAVE COME TO DESTR OY YOU>>
3	1	9m	1	0	1.0	X			Morph to animals / It sounds fantastic
4	1	8m	1	0	1.0	X			X
5	1	9m	1	0	1.0	X			Tearing apart...
6	1	8m	1	0	1.0				The teeth ripped the Andalite apart. <This makes me sad

7	1	7m							X
8	1	9m	1	0	1.0				Tobias chasing the string<It's hilarious
9	1	8m	1	0	1.0				YOU'RE HAPPY <CUTE
10	1	9m	1	0	1.0				"Math teachers, for sure," < 100% sure
11	1	8m	1	0	1.0				Your brother is a Controller."< This makes me scary
12	1	7m	1	0	1.0				X
13	1	8m	1	0	1.0				Poor tom...
14	1	10\m	1	0	1.0				They're so perfectly normal it's abnormal.< I like this sentence
15	1	8m	1	0	1.0				They were everywhere.

									Everyw here!<< Hehe
16	1	9m	1	0	1.0				Nooooo ooooo o! < Poor jake. He ate a spider.
17	1	7m	1	0	1.0				It was right under my school. < Terrable ...
18	1	6m	1	0	1.0				"Idiot teenage rs with a death wish," Marco said. < I love marco's word's
19	1	11m	1	0	1.0				"Steal a golf cart?"<< I LOVE IT.
20	1	8m	1	0	1.0				"Ten seconds ? Ten seconds ?"
21	1	9m	1	0	1.0				X
22	1	8m	1	0	1.0				X
23	1	9m	1	0	1.0				And she was

									getting very, very large. > go and kill everything!!!
24	1	6m	1	0	1.0				<Puny little nothing! > perfect.
25	1	7m	1	0	1.0				We were not going to make it.
26	1	8m	1	0	1.0				It was Tom.
27	1	5m	1	0	1.0				<It's okay, Jake. Like you said, we're alive.>

Student 2 Reading/listening LOG

Chapter	Times Read	Timed Reading	Times Listened	Pauses	Listening (speed)	Most challenging part?	How did you understand and the main idea?	Difficult words & spelling strategies?	Most interesting part? Why?
1	2	8'49"	2	3	1.0	Last part of chapter when the main character finds something weird.	Main character, Rachel, Cassie, Marco and Tobias	Andalite, Sleazetroll, chainsaw, flying sawcer	X

							found something weird heading back home.		
2	2	8'50"	1	2	1.0	X	They met someone who was on the ship. And they want to help alien. Other alien were here to destroy them.	zap, dweeb	When the main character introduced the figure of alien.
3	1	5'41"	5	6	1.0	the part starting from " the year of parasites"	Alien asked to get a blue box on the ship. Alien wanted to give power which we can become an animal	memes Yerkes Andalite Morph	C
4	2	4'58"	4	9	1.0	Most part of the chapter.	Alien said not to be an animal for more than two hours. An alien says		X

							Yerks are here so said to run. They found yerks.		
5	2	5'32"	3	9	1.0	the part that yerks are trying to threaten them	the reason why Yerks wanted to destroy people is they're so weak and so many. Yerks is trying to destroy the people who is on earth.	vicious Centipe de Visser 3	X
6	2	3'45"	2	3	1.0	X	Yerks had a fight with them and he found that it was a dream.		X
7	2	4'16"	3	6	1.0	X	Tobias came to Jake's house. Tobias said that He was dude last night which is his cat.	groaned Radio active Morph Grin Protruding	Tobias becoming cat.

							and Tobias is explaining being a cat to Jake. Jake can not believe everything, so Tobias showed Jake being cat.		
8	2	2'01"	1	3	1.0	X	Tobias who became cat talked with Jake and sent thoughts. And Tobias changed back to human. Tobias said to Jake he is the leader so they must defeat and Jake went to find his dog.		The part that Jake and Tobias playing with strings.
9	2	3'42"	2	5	1.0	X	Tobias said becoming the animal	nuts trance Tucked	The process of Jake being dog.

							we have to think about animal we want to become . Jake became dog. Jake's brother Tom came to room and laughed.		
10	2	3'52"	2	6	1.0	X	Tom and Jake talked each other. And Tom quitted Basketb all team. On the newspaper said Cops found out there's alien. Cassie became horse and Marco surprised .	Thrust munch Infiltrate d Ballistic	X
11	2	4'20"	1	5	1.0	X	Cops came to them. Fortunately, Casie	X	X

							became human. Marco and Jack tried to become normal. Tom heard that playing kids doing fireworks . Tom asked to participate sharing.		
12	2	4'10"	3	8	1.0	When explaining yerks pool.	Marco was curious that Tom is interested about construction site. They found a hawk and it is Tobias. Tobias felt happy being a hawk. And they decided to fight for Andalite.	gnarled Tilted Talons Thermal s	When Marco is telling Jake that Tom might be one of them. And when Tobias changed to hawk.
13	2	5'36"	2	3	1.0	X	They found Yeerks pool.	Taxxons coed	X

							Tobias thought Tom and Cops were maybe the controller . They decided to attend a meeting of sharing. Jake was surprised that Tom has a different view of looking at him.		
14	2	5'10"	4	2	1.0	X	Cassie said the sharing is not a normal place. Jake is trying to sneak into the meeting. Tobias changed to be a hawk. Jake changed to homer and found his assistant principle	Abnormal cult Scampering Nosal* nuzzled frantically	When Jake changed to become homer.
15	2	5'41"	5	9	1.0	X	Tom is	Slunk	X

							trying to kill Jake. Jake found Tom is a controller .Police told Cassie to go out. Jake and they went back to them. They are trying to fight with controllers.		
16	2	4'10"	2	3	1.0	X	Jake turned into a lizard. Jake ran. Jake went to Chapman's office. Jake saw a spider and tasted it.	Crouch bolder	X
17	2	2'36"	3	5	1.0	X	Jake's tail was caught. Jake followed Chapman. Someone was caught in brain by yeerks and Jake	Snappe d off	When Jake found a Yeerk pool.

							found the yeerk pool.		
18	2	3'15"	4	2	1.0	Most part of the chapter.	They are planning to go to Yeerks pool. Tobias said he will go together. And they are trying to save Tom. and named the team animorph h.	X	X
19	4	7'13"	5	1	1.0	X	They went to exhibit and see what animals there. And Marco gave apple to Gorilla. They were found by a guard. Also Marco morphed into a tiger..	Margins	X
20	3	3'57"	2	4	1.0	X	Jake felt lots of confiden	X	X

							ce because tiger had lots of confiden ce. And they ran to the ladder.		
21	2	3'50"	2	5	1.0	X	Jake came back home and taking with Tom. Tom was trying to go to Yeerks pool. Cassie was not home for dinner. They went to Yeerks pool and they found Cassie was there.	Clench	X
22	1	3'44"	2	2	1.0	X	Cassie was in Yeerks pool with the guard. They found a cage in an unimagin able	X	X

							place.		
23	2	2'42"	2	2	1.0	X	People are caught by Yeerks and they fought but lose. Yeerks are trying to change Cassie into a host. Tom was not voluntarily joining the sharing.	Slithering maggots taxon	X
24	1	1'36"	1	2	1.0	X	Rachel morphed into a gigantic animal. which is an elephant. and Rachel threw the man. and Jake became tiger.	X	When Rachel threw man when she morphed into an elephant.
25	2	2'45"	2	3	1.0	X	Marco became Big Jim. Jake saved Tom. and Cassie became	X	X

							a horse. Visser three found that they are a Andelites .		
26	2	2'17"	2	2	1.0	X	They were trying to run from Visser three. and the fireball has exploded .	plural	X
27	2	2'09"	3	1	1.0	X	Jake told to Tom about he was a tiger. Tobias became hawk forever.	X	X

Student 3 Reading/listening LOG

Chapter	Time s Read	Timed Reading	Times Listened	Pause s	Listening (speed)	Most challenging part?	How did you understand and the main idea?	Difficult words & spelling strategies?	Most interesting part? Why?
1	2	7(one time)	3	2	1	It was difficult overall to understand because it was the	Five friends found something strange on their	sleaze troll	x

						first time I started.	way home and the adventure begins.		
2	2	9	2	2	0.75	x	Friends got to meet aliens in places like ufo and wanted to help him.	bandage	The fact that there are more aliens out there
3	3	12	2	1	0.75	The conversation with aliens was difficult.	An alien asked his friends to bring him a box and decided to give him the magic of turning into an animal.	yark	The contents of friends venturing to do the alien's favor were interesting.
4	3	11	4	2	1	Most of the content was difficult.	Another alien appears and the friends run away.	stumble	x
5	3	13	4	2	1	Most of the content was	Another alien tried to attack	sneer	The urgent content was

						difficult.	people on Earth.		interesting in the confrontation with aliens.
6	2	9	4	2	0.75	The latter part was difficult.	I fought with another alien and it was a dream(? ...)	control	x
7	3	8	5	3	1	Most of the content was difficult.	The conflict and responsibility that arise as human lives and realities change, and the struggle to adapt to those changes.	Andalite	The moment when Tobias transforms into his pet cat, Dude, proving that the transformation is real.
8	2	7	4	3	1	Most of the content was difficult.	The responsibility and conflict of the protagonists using their new powers to fight to	mutter	Tobias feeling his cat instincts and acting like a cat while still being aware

							protect Earth.		of his human side.
9	3	9	3	4	0.75	Most of the content was difficult.	The struggle to maintain personal identity and control while adapting to the overwhelming instincts and sensations of an animal form.	Visser	Jake transforming into a dog and experiencing the world through a dog's senses, including the overwhelming smells and emotions.
10	3	11	4	2	1	x	The internal struggle of the group as they weigh the risks of continuing their fight against the Yeerks and the consequences it may have on their personal	skintight	The group realizing that the police are searching for them after seeing the newspaper article, and Marco's emotional reaction to the danger they

							lives.		face.
11	4	9	3	2	1	x	The conflict between the need to protect the world from the Yeerks and the personal challenges of dealing with family and trust.	punk	The realization that Jake's brother, Tom, is a Controller, which deepens the sense of danger and mistrust.
12	3	10	5	3	1	Most of the content was difficult.	The internal struggle of the characters as they grapple with the weight of their responsibility to fight the Yeerks, despite the personal challenges and risks	Kandrona	x

							involved.		
13	2	12	1	2	1				
14	3	9	1	2	1				
15	2	9	1	2	1				
16	2	8	2	2	1				
17	2	14	2	3	1				
18	2	11	1	2	1				
19	3	12	2	3	1				
20	3	11	1	3	1				
21	3	11	1	2	1				
22	2	9	1	2	1				
23	2	10	2	1	1				
24	2	8	2	2	0.75				
25	2	10	1	2	0.75				
26	3	11	2	3	1				
27	2	13	2	2	1				

APPENDIX I: STUDENTS' ANSWERS TO THE TESTS

Chapters 1-12

Questions	S1- RBL Test 1	S1- Test 2	S2-LBR Test 1	S2- Test 2	S3- LBR Test 1	S3- Test 2
1. What are the names of the five kids?	Tom(...), marco, tovias, cassie, tovias	Jake, Tovia, Cassie, Marco, Rachel	Jake, Rachel, Cassie, Marco and Tobias	Jake, Marco, Tobias, Cassie, Rachel	Jake, Marco, Rachel, Tobias, Cassy	Jake, Marco, Tobias, Rachel, Cassie
2. Who is the narrator of the story?	Can not remember	Can not remember	Jake	Jake	Jake	Jake
3. What do Jake and Marco like to do for fun?	vedio games	Video games				They are playing video games and hanging out at store that sells comic books.
4. What is Jake's brother's name?	Tom	Tom	Tom	Tom	Tom	Tom
5. What is the name of the first alien race introduced?	andalite	andalities	andalite	andalite	andalite	andalites
6. What shape is the Andalite spaceship?	sause	A flying sasuer	UFO	Ufo shape	UFO	Spaceship's shape is pod
7. How does the Andalite communicate?	In mins	With their minds	They communicate by their thoughts	By human words		Anadlite doesn't use sound, it communicates telepath
8. How many eyes does an Andalite have?	three	More than three		4	10	Andalite has four eyes

9.What is the Andalite's name?	It was very long and complicated	Prince....bla blabla		Visser three		Elfangor
10. What special ability does the Andalite give to the kids?	morph	morphing	Becoming an animal	animorph	To turn into an animal	Andalite gives kids morph into animal
11.How do the kids acquire the ability to morph?	To touch the animals	toching a blue box by an introduce by andalite	Thinking about the the animal that they are close to or they want to become	Andalite gave it to them		They touch Andalite's cube
12. What is the maximum time the kids can stay in animal form?	2H	2 hours in earth time	2 hours	2 hours	2 hours	The maximum time kids can stay animal is 2 hours
13. What happens if they stay past the time limite?	Can not turn back	They might not come back to human form	They couldn't turn back to human	They couldn't become human again		They can't come back to their original bodies
14. What is the name of hte aline species that takes over human bodies?	yeerks	yeerks	yeerks	yeerks	visser	yeerks
15. Where do the yeerks enter a persons body?	Nose and mouth to the brain	Nose and mouth	Human's brain	Ear canal	ears	ears
16. What is the title given to a Yeerk leader?	Blablalal three	Visser Three		Visser three		Visser

17. What is the name of the organization Tom is involved in?	Can no remember	sharing	sharing	The sharing		
18. What kind of animal does Tobias morph into first?	His cat	Dude (his cat)	cat	dude	hawk	hawk
19. What do yeerks need to survive every three days?	shower?	They go to a pond for resting		They have to go to yeerk's pool		Yeerks leave host body every three days
20. Where do the kids meet discuss their plans?	Can't remember	forgot	Cassie's farm	In cassie's farm	police	Shopping mall
21. How do the yeerks control their human hosts?	well	Control their brain, thoughts and minds				infestation
22. What happens to a host when a yeerk leaves their body?	Be dead maybe	Die maybe				
23. What do yeerks use to feed their species?	pond	Eat other species			Yeerk pools	Yeerk pool
24. What does the andaliate warn the kids kids before he dies?	Beware of controller	Fight with yeerks before they damage human environment	Do not let the yeerks to find them		Anadalite warns the kids about yeerks invasion and stopping yeerks from Earth
25. What	They forget	They forget	They get		They don't	They have

happens when the kids first attempt to morph?	their clothes	their clothes	really scared but as soon as they get used to it, they have fun		know how to control animal instinct	hard to control instincts of animals
26. Why does tobias have trouble morphing back?	Because he doesn't like his human form	Because he doesn't like his human form	Because it took more than 2 hours	Because Tobias stayed more than 2 hours in Animorphs form		Tobias stayed more than 2 hours so he has a problem that returns his original form
27. What do the kids discover about the Yeerk pool?	ewwww	They discover that they might blow up the pool and kill every yeerks				They know that they have to destroy the yeerk pool
28. Who is Visser Three, and why is he important?	Tom or the police	He is an Andalite and he orders the other yeerks	Because Visser Three is the top of the group	Visser Three is the leader of the Andalites	controller	He is the main enemy
29. Why do you think the Andalite chooses to give the morphing ability to the kids instead of fighting the yeerks himself?	Because he was dying.	Because the Andalite was dying	Because the Andalite was almost dying and Yeerks will not know that they will change to an animal.	Because the Andalite is about to die		Think it's because he's hurt a lot
30. Why is Tom so eager to recruit Jake into the Sharing?	Because he needs to pick up more yeerks.	Because he might be the one of the kids who have seen yeerks and Andalites	Because it's his brother and Tom noticed something weird with Jake.	Because Tom wanted to control Jake as a controller		Because Tom was already being controlled by the controller
31. How do the Andalites and yeerks differ in their goals?	Peace and war	Andalites: kind and gentle/Yeerks: kill things	Andalites want to save the human environment but Yeerks want to	Andalites want to save the Earth but Yeerks want to destroy the		Andalites are trying to protect other species, and Yeerks are trying to

			destroy human environment	Earth		manipulate and dominate.
32. What clues suggest that Jake is becoming leader of the group?	Can't remember	He is the most bravest kid	Because Jake gave a blue box to Andalite.	Because Jake helped Andalite to get boxes		His decisive action and responsibility
33. Why Tobias enjoy being a hawk more than the others enjoy their morphs?	Because it is free. Flying is wonderful	Because flying is fantastic	Because it has a lot of freedom.	Because hawk has more freedom and great sight than other animals		This is because of the freedom of flight that people do not feel when they are people and the sense of freedom they feel in the sky.
34. Why does Visser Three seem more dangerous than other controllers?	Because it is the head of them.	Because he can morph to others.		Because Visser Three is Andalite's host		
35. Why might be the kids be hesitant to trust anyone outside their group?	Someone might be a controller	They might be a controller out there	Because anyone who says about those things they might be a controller or might be caught in cops.	Because outside people can be changed to controllers	Because their ability is dangerous and very secret	Because anyone can be manipulated by the yeerks.
36. What are some risks of using their morphing ability in public?	Outfit issue	1-they might get a call from 911 or similar 2-clothes issue	They might be caught by cops.	They can be caught by cops	Exposure of friends' original figure	Their secrets can be exposed and they can be attacked by Yeerks.

37. Why is the time limit for morphing important to the story?	Because they are living a life at the human world	Because the kids each have a family.	Because Yeerks will found out that humans are disturbing Yeerks from destroying human creatures.	Because it helps them to hide that they are human	If they don't come back in time they can't get back to their original body	If they don't come back in time, it gives tension because they can be in danger.
38. What could happen if the yeerks discovered that the kids had the morphing power?	Kill every animal	Obviously get killed	They will found out and try to kill animals which kids can change to animals.	Human creatures will be destroyed and the Earth will be controlled by Yeerks and controller		
39. Do you think the andalite made the right decision by giving the morphing power to the kids? Why or why not?		No because they are just bunch of small kids after all	No, because they are too young. And only 5 of them can do it so it's too small people.	I think no because they are too young to handle those kind of problem.	I think that is the right decision. Because they can fight against yeerk.	I think Andalite's decision to give children the ability to transform was right because their pure courage and determination can lead to great change.
40. If you were in Jakes position would you trust the andalite? Why?	Every power has a warning, and you must listen to it. or you will be doomed.	Trust. Because aliens are fantastic and the situation is awesome	No, because I believe that Alien is not exist on the planet.	I will not trust Andalite because it is not real exist alien and it can be dangerous.	I trust Andalite. Because he give me a power (ability) and to help friends.	I will believe it because he provided important information and helped the children.
41. How does the theme of power and control play a role in the story?	I would trust them. because it sounds fantastic and exciting.	Every power has a limit and controlling is necessary	Power by Yeerks who is controlling Earth.	Yeerks control the world		
42. Do you	They might	Stop the	I think kids	Try to stop.	I think kids	The children

think the kids should try to stop the yeerks or just stay out of it? explain	stop them. Because... that's the way the story continues...	yeerks. It's difficult and dangerous but some people must save the world and all.	should stop the Yeerks. Because Andalite gave the power to morph so they need to use this power in real life and they need to save the earth.	because they got a power to animorph from Andalite so they should be responsible of the thing that they thought they should do.	need to help. Because yeerks are trying to attack people on earth in danger and even police are hiding this fact.	should try to stop Yeerk because if Yeerk does not stop threatening to take over the Earth, human and the entire planet will be in danger.
43. What ethical issues do you see with the idea of morphing into another living being?	Can not think about it. morphing just sound fantastic to me...	I think there is no issues about it	They will have less humans to protect in human life.	They will kill lots of creatures also they will have lots of duplicate of people.		A moral problem
44. If you had the ability to morph what animal would you choose and why?	shark or a whale - i like swimming, thus, I sometimes have a dream breathing under water.	Whale or turtle. Live long, and swimming under water is a happy thing.	Tiger. Because tigers are fast at running and the looking of tiger made me to move back. And most of people are scared of tigers.	Lizard. because they can change to any color and also they are not seen very well.	I choose bird. I want to become a bird and fly wherever I want.	I want to feel like flying in the sky.
45. What lessons can be learned from the kids choices in the story?	DO NOT BRAKE THE RULES / and sometimes have fun going to the wildness...	Don't go to dangerous places or you will have to save the earth.	The lessons that I learned from kids are they are so brave to accept Andalite's request and there thinking of humans.	If we want to help someone, think carefully and think if they can be responsible of that choice.	I learned to solve problems through their teamwork.	responsibility, courage, and cooperation

Chapters 13-27

Questions	S1- LBR Test 1	S1- Test 2	S2-RBL Test 1	S2- Test 2	S3- RBL Test 1	S3- Test 2
1. What does Tobias suggest The Sharing is?		A yeerk pool	Tobis said it is controlled	Tobias suggested that this is the organization for yeerks	Sharing is an organization for controllers	Tobias suggests that the Sharing is an organization for Controllers
2. Where was the sharing meeting?	In the beach	beach	The sharing meetings are held in beach	Near by beach	On the beach	At a bonfire beach
3. What animal does Jake morph into at the sharing meeting?	A stray dog	dog	Jake morphed into lizard.	dog	dog	Jake morphs into his dog Homer
4. What person from Jake's school was at the Sharing meeting?	Principal aka Mr. Chapman	Chapman	Mr. Chapman	Assistant principal	Principal at Jake's school	Jake's school at the sharing meeting is Assistant principal Chapman
5. What kind of lizard did Jake morph into?	Geko lizard??	Geko lizard	Green lizard	Green anole	Anole lizard	gecko
6. Where did he morph?	His closet	In his cabinet	school	Locker at school	Jake morphed inside his locker	Jake morph in Cassie's barn
7. What did he eat when he was a lizard?	spider	spider!	He ate a living spider	spider	He ate spider	Jake ate a spider
8. What body part did the shoe step on?	tale	tail	tail	tail		The shoe stepped on Jake's tail.

9. Where did Jake follow Mr. Chapman?	Janitor's office	Janitor's office	The where sharing meeting held	Secret entrance of the yeerks pool	Jake followed Mr. Chapman to the mall	Jake followed Mr. Chapman's office
10. What did Jake hear in that room?	Locking sounds	People screaming	Human scream	Talked about where is yeerks pool	In that room Jake heard about plans	The yeerks talking
11. What do the kids decide to do with the yeerks?	They decided to morph to beasts and big animals	Fight with them	They decided to fight yeerks and make a group called Animorphs	Decided to fight with yeerks	Stop yeerks	The kids decide to fight back against the yeerks
12. Who suggests the name Animorphs?	Marco	Marco	Rachel	Marco	Marco	Marco suggests the name
13. What kind of animal is Big Jim?	gorilla	gorilla	gorilla	gorila	Big Jim is gorilla	gorilla
14. Who gets Big Jim's DNA?	Marco	Marco	Jake	Marco	Marco get Big Jim's DNA	Cassie gets Big Jim's DNA
15. What animal exhibit did Jake and Marco run into?	Tiger	Tiger			Jake and marco run into the tiger exhibit	Jake and Marco run into the tiger exhibit
16. Who touches the animal in the exhibit?	Jake	Jake	Marco	jake	Jake touched the tiger	Marco touches the animal which is the tiger
17. What food does Jake's mom tell him to eat?	broccoli	broccoli	broccoli	broccoli	broccoli	Jake mom tells him to eat apples
18. Who has Cassie?	horse	Can not understand this question	controller	The controllers	Controller policeman has Cassie	The controllers have Cassie

19. How do the kids go into the Janitor's office?	sneaking	Pretend to be controller	By hearing from Mr. Chapman	They morph into animal before going into Janitor's office	They walk down the stairs	They enter the Janitor's office by crawling through science lab
20. Where are the people without yeerks placed?	jail	In the jail	People without yeerks are placed in secret place	They are placed in hidden places	cage?	Placed in cages
21. What are collaborators?	Who are	Those who chose to be a side of yeerks	Collaborators work to help yeerks	Collaborators are volunteer to be with yeerks	Collaborators are humans and hork bajir	Collaborators are humans or Hork Bajir who allow yeerks to their brains and control them
22. What animal do you think Rachel turns into?	elephant	elephant	Tiger because she has a strong mind.	elephant	Rachel turns into an elephant	elephant
23. What animal did Jake turn into?	tiger	tiger	cat	tiger	Jake turns into tiger	Jake turns into tiger
24. What does Marco tell everyone to call him?	Big kong	King Kong		The Marco	Marco tells everyone to call him King Kong	Marco tells everyone to call him King Kong.
25. What body part did Tobias attack on the Hork Bajir?	eye	eye	Hork bajir's eyes	eyes	Hork Bajir's eyes	eyes
26. Who does Visser Three think the kids are?	anadlites	anadlites	Just a human	andalites		Visser Three thinks the kids are andalites
27. What did	Fire ball	fireball	fireballs	fireballs	Visser Three	Visser Three

Visser Three Shoot at the kids?					shoot fireballs at the kids	shot fireballs at the kids.
28. Who do the Animoprhs rescue?	Dosen of people who was a controller	Human and tom	Tom	Tom	Humans and two Hork Bajir	The Animorphs rescue one human, the woman, who rode Cassie's back up stairs
29. How do the animorphs feel about fighting the yeerks?	scary	Scared, horror, worried	They will feel scary because yeerks look like so scary to me.	They feel scared but thye have a responsibility of fighting yeerks.	They feel is very hard and difficult. But they protect the Earth.	The animorphs feel that fighting the yeerks is necessary but exhausting and terrifying battle.
30. Why does Marco suggest the name Animorphs?	Animal + morphs	Because its simple	I think it is a mixed word between Animal and morph.	Because they are morphing to animal.	Because they can morph into animals.	Because it describes their ability to morph into animals
31. Why is Jake's ability to morph into a tiger significant?	Because he has the ability of courage and power	He had power and brave.	It is significant to because it helps him to save Tom and Cassie.	It symbolizes that Jake is leader of the group because tiger is king of the animal world.	This makes him powerful fighter against the yeerks.	Because it givens him powerful advantage in combat
32. Why do the Animorphs go to the sharing meeting?	They need to seef it's a controllers party.	To find out who is the controller.	To know what their enemies are planning to do.	To find ou information about yeerks and about yeerks pool		Because they are investigating the yeerks and trying to gether information.
33. What does Jake eating a	The part of the animal brain has	That the brain of the animal is still	Because lizard has a long tongue	That means Jake is losing	Becoming more animalistic.	He is accepting the instincts

spider as a lizard suggest?	the weight.	strong.	and he animorphed to lizard so he can play only role of lizard.	human consciousness		and behaviors of the animal he has morphed into.
34. Why do they pretend to be Controllors to enter the Janitor's office?	Because it will be the answer	So no one can stop them.	Because it be dangerous if they are not pretending to be a controller.	Because they can be caught or be suspected by other controllers	They pretend to be controllers to avoid suspicion.	Because they need to gather information and search for clues about the yeerks.
35. Why do voluntary hosts exist?	They are persuaded by visser three	Because they are convinced by visser three	To infest yeerks	They can have better hope or treatment about negotiating.		Because some humans willingly allow a yeerk to take control of their minds and bodies.
36. How does Tobias staying in hawk form impact him?	He can be free?	free	By staying in a hawk he could have wild sight and could see a lot of thing which is far away.	Tobias need to fight everytime with yeerks	The longer Tobias stay in hawk, the harder it becomes for him to remain his human nature.	Signifies emotional and psychological impact.
37. What does Visser Three shooting fireballs tell us about him?	He is violent	He is violent	Visser three is shooting a fireball because they need to show aggression against them	Visser three is enjoying the fight between andalites and visser three.	It shows huge power	Visser three shooting fireballs tells us that he is extremely dangerous, powerful
38. Why does Tobias believe more andalites will come?	To save the earth	Because they are kind aliens	To help Tobias to morph back to human and realizing yeerks dominated	To help Tobias morph back to human to give lots of power to morph.	Because Tobias trust andalites.	Because he holds onto the hope that they will eventually come to Earth's aid

			Earth			in the battle against the yeerks.
39. Do you think Jake is a leader?	Yes because he can do brave things.	Yeeees because he is brave.	I think Jake is quite a good leader because he is trying to do most things first than other kids.	I think Jake is a good leader. because he has a leadership to care of their friends.	I think he is a good leader. He shows courage, responsibility, and the ability to make hard decisions. His leadership is not perfect but he shows growth.	Yes. Jake is a good leader. He is brave, strategic, and he also shows compassion.
40. What would you do if you were offered the ability to morph?	I will turn into a whale and leave the hometown and live in the sea.	Become a whale and go to the sea.	If I have a ability to morph, I think I would do hunting and give to my mom and cook for our family dinner.	If i wer offered the ability to morph, I will be friends with animals.	I experience the world from their perspective.	I would be cautious but curious. I would experiment with different animals to learn more about their strengths and abilities.
41. How do the animorphs choices compare to real-world resistance movements ?	similar	It is hard to say. But i think its kind of similar and more touch to the issue.		They are brave and to try others.		The animorphs choices mirror real world resistance movements by risking their lives.
42. Do you think Marco's humor helps or hurts the team?	Both because kids are delicate and young.	Eventually helps because I like sarcasm.	I think Marco's humor helps. Because in tough situations, he makes team lightened.	I think Marco's humor helped the team. because morphing is the first time for everybody in the team so	It was helping because it had lots of freezing situation but it helped to make others calm.	Marco's humor helps the team by lightening the mood in tough situations, though it can also distract or downplay

				they were scared but because of Marco's humor they felt little scared.		the severity of their mission.
43. What ethical delimitas do the Animorphs face in their fight?	Killing aliens maybe	1.about their life/2. About to kill or hurt something.	Using animals to fight, putting innocent lives at risk.	The ethical issues are killing morality. because it is related with living and death.	They will kill lots of humans who could not morph.	The Animorphs face ethical dilemmas like using animals' DNA for war, causing harm to others, and deciding whether to risk innocent lives in their fight against the Yeerks.
44. How do you feel about Tobias' decision to stay as a hawk?	Its very sad (I cried) but its good for him. He always wanted to be a hawk.	Very sad... but I think its the best way for Tobias.	It feels sad because Tobias was also important in this team and also when the fight is over with Yeerks, Tobias could not be friend comfortably.	I felt really sad. because Tobias sacrificed himself for friends.	It shows the emotional pain of losing his humanity.	Tobias' decision to stay as a hawk is heartbreaking, as it shows his sacrifice and struggle with his identity.
45. If you could change on thing about how the Animorphs operate, what would it be?	Clothes issue	Clothes issue	It will be more than 2 hours. I will extend to 12 hours.	I will extend the time limit of morphing.		I would change their secrecy, as it sometimes isolates them and limits their ability to seek help from trusted allies.